

Residual Value Estimation for Electric Vehicles

Master's Thesis

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Zusammenfassung

Abstract

The residual value (RV) of an electric vehicle (EV) reflects its expected market worth after a period of use and plays an important role in leasing, financing, and fleet management decisions. However, forecasting EV residual value remains challenging due to battery degradation, rapid technological change, evolving policy frameworks, and overall market volatility. Existing approaches mainly rely on historical resale data and machine learning, but often assume relatively stable conditions and do not fully capture real-world uncertainties such as second-life battery potential or changes in government incentives.

This study develops a scenario-aware residual value estimation framework by combining qualitative expert insights with quantitative machine-learning modeling. Five industry experts from battery engineering, asset finance, vehicle valuation, and fleet total-cost-of-ownership analysis were interviewed to identify key RV drivers and support hypothesis development. A stacking ensemble model—combining XGBoost, AdaBoost, and CatBoost as base learners with a linear meta-learner—was trained on used-car listings from AutoScout24 (Germany) matched against new-vehicle catalog prices. The stacking model achieved the best predictive performance with RMSE = 10.26%, MAE = 7.72%, $R^2 = 0.763$, and MAPE = 12.89%, outperforming all individual base models. The results show that vehicle age and mileage are the dominant drivers of residual value, acting as practical proxies for battery condition. Technical characteristics, particularly battery capacity and driving range, further influence value by capturing technological competitiveness, while brand effects introduce an additional categorical dimension. Scenario analysis across multiple market conditions indicates that average residual values remain relatively stable, but downside risk varies substantially across scenarios. This highlights the importance of distribution-based evaluation rather than relying on single-point estimates when assessing residual value under uncertainty.

The study provides a transparent and reproducible work that combines expert knowledge with data-driven modeling, supporting more robust decision-making in the used EV market. Future improvements will depend primarily on the availability of standardized battery health data and longitudinal price observations.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

Electric vehicles (EVs) are becoming an important part of both passenger and commercial transport, supported by rising environmental concerns and strong regulatory support across Europe. According to the International Energy Agency, global EV sales exceeded 17 million units in 2024, where Europe represents a substantial share of this growth [16]. At the same time, governments continue to promote EV adoption through different measures such as purchase incentives, tax benefits, and low-emission zones, while at the same time tightening restrictions on internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles. [38,42,46].

Despite this progress, one major barrier persists: the uncertainty surrounding the *residual value* (RV) of used EVs. Unlike traditional ICE vehicles, EVs present unique valuation challenges. Battery degradation, rapid technological improvements, and evolving policy landscapes make it difficult to forecast how much an EV will be worth after several years of use [9, 22, 40]. This lack of predictability poses financial risks for leasing companies, fleet managers, and private buyers alike. In many cases, uncertainty around battery health and resale conditions leads consumers to choose used ICE vehicles over EVs [1,22]. It is also worth noting that the EV-specific residual value challenge is directly dependent on battery economics: battery pack costs have declined by more than 90% since 2010 [30, 49], meaning that successive EV generations offer substantially more range per unit cost, creating a technological obsolescence dynamic without parallel in ICE vehicle markets. At the same time, questions about battery degradation and end-of-life management—including second-life repurposing [29, 33] and recycling [14]—directly shape market perceptions of used-EV value and motivate several of the modeling choices described in Chapter 4.

Furthermore, most traditional residual value models are based on historical trends and fail to capture forward-looking scenarios or EV-specific factors such as second-life battery use and charging behavior [12,26]. This methodological gap limits their relevance in an increasingly EV-dominated marketplace.

This study aims to investigate the main factors influencing the residual value of electric vehicles and explore how these drivers shape second-hand EV market dynamics. The core goal is to develop a scenario-based model that simulates how EV residual values could evolve under different future conditions—considering battery performance, second-life potential, and policy developments [27]. By focusing on light commercial EV vehicles in Germany and combining new-vehicle catalog data

with real-world resale listings, the research delivers insights that are both academically grounded and practically applicable. It also contributes to a more informed and confident transition toward EV ownership in the second-hand market.

1.2. Thesis Objectives

This thesis aims to investigate the nature of electric vehicle value, identify the key drivers of its depreciation, and model the residual value of EVs under uncertainty. The specific objectives are:

1. To identify and quantify the key technical, market, and policy-related factors that influence EV residual value, drawing on both literature and expert knowledge.
2. To explore expert perspectives on dominant RV drivers and the measurement practices used in industry valuation.
3. To develop and empirically test hypotheses derived from the literature and expert interviews using a data-driven modeling approach.
4. To build a stacking ensemble model that predicts the depreciated residual value percentage of electric vehicles.
5. To simulate how EV residual values evolve under different market and policy scenarios (Optimistic, Moderate, Pessimistic, and Wild-card).
6. To assess the potential contribution of second-life battery reuse to EV value retention.

Each objective directly addresses the core problem: the absence of reliable, forward-looking, and context-aware methods for estimating EV residual value in a rapidly evolving market.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Traditional Residual Value Estimation Methods

Residual value estimation traditionally relied on *statistical and econometric techniques* derived from resale transaction data. These approaches remain attractive due to their transparency and statistical rigor, which is critical in financial analysis, but they cannot capture non-linear relationships, battery-specific effects, or forward-looking policy impacts.

A representative example is the study conducted by Argonne National Laboratory [38], which compared depreciation patterns of ICE, hybrid, plug-in hybrid (PHEV), and battery electric vehicles (BEV) using three conventional approaches. Each approach has distinct strengths and limitations that have shaped the direction of more recent machine-learning-based methods.

Snapshot Method

The snapshot method computes residual value at a fixed vehicle age by means of the *Adjusted Retention Rate (ARR)*, defined as the ratio of the used resale price to the original manufacturer list price at a given point in time. ARR snapshot estimates are widely used in the leasing industry as intuitive, easily communicable benchmarks: a three-year, 60,000-km vehicle in a given segment retains, say, 45% of its original list price. The simplicity of this measure makes it accessible to non-specialist stakeholders, and it serves as the basis for residual value guarantees in many standard lease agreements. However, snapshot estimates disregard the complete depreciation trajectory—they capture only a single point in the vehicle’s life cycle—and are highly sensitive to short-term market conditions at the observation date. A snapshot taken during a period of used-car price inflation (as observed globally during 2021–2022 due to new-car supply shortages) will overstate the structural retention rate, leading to residual value guarantees that cannot be met under normal market conditions [44].

Time-Series Method

Time-series models reconstruct depreciation trends by following specific vehicle models over multiple age observation points, fitting a curve to the declining ARR as a function of age and mileage. These models are more informative than static snapshots because they characterize the full depreciation trajectory, reveal systematic

differences in depreciation speed across powertrains and segments, and can identify inflection points where depreciation accelerates or decelerates. Argonne’s time-series analysis [38] showed that BEVs exhibit a steeper initial depreciation slope but a flatter trajectory in later years compared with ICE vehicles—a pattern consistent with technological obsolescence effects early in the vehicle’s life, when newer-generation EVs enter the market. Despite these advantages, time-series methods require extensive longitudinal data collected at multiple age points for the same vehicle models, and they implicitly assume that historical depreciation patterns will repeat—an assumption that is particularly fragile in the context of EVs, where battery technology, policy incentives, and consumer expectations are changing rapidly.

Econometric Regression Models

Econometric approaches such as weighted least squares regressions model the ARR as a function of observable vehicle and market attributes, including powertrain type, vehicle size, market segment, and luxury classification. Regression models provide parameter estimates that are statistically interpretable and can be validated against theory: a significant negative coefficient on vehicle age confirms the expected depreciation-with-time relationship, while a significant positive coefficient on luxury classification confirms the brand premium hypothesis. Argonne’s regression analysis [38] found that BEVs retained systematically lower values than ICEs even after controlling for these attributes, while luxury segment vehicles showed superior retention regardless of powertrain type. This finding motivated the inclusion of both brand affiliation and original list price as features in the present thesis.

The limitation of econometric regression in the EV context is its assumption of linear or log-linear relationships between the predictors and ARR. As subsequent EV-specific studies have shown [12, 40], the mechanisms that drive EV depreciation—battery degradation curves, technological obsolescence step-changes, and policy discontinuities—are inherently non-linear and interact in ways that linear regression cannot represent without extensive manual feature engineering.

Scenario-Based Macroeconomic Forecasting

Beyond purely statistical techniques, Moody’s *AutoCycle*TM model [28] demonstrated the potential of scenario-based forecasting for residual value management. The model links vehicle-level descriptors (VIN, mileage, region, condition) with macroeconomic stress variables—including GDP growth, oil prices, and interest rates—to generate forward-looking residual value estimates and stress-test leasing portfolios under adverse economic conditions. *AutoCycle* is particularly valuable for financial risk management because it explicitly represents the dependence of used-vehicle prices on macroeconomic factors, allowing leasing companies to quantify their residual value exposure under recession or oil-price-shock scenarios. While innovative, *AutoCycle* focuses primarily on macroeconomic levers applicable to ICE

vehicles and lacks EV-specific elements such as battery-related depreciation, technological obsolescence, or policy sensitivity—limitations that directly motivated the scenario framework adopted in the present thesis.

2.2. EV-Specific Residual Value Estimation

Unlike ICE vehicles, whose depreciation patterns are relatively stable, EV residual values are driven by non-linear interactions among *battery health*, *technology evolution*, and *policy incentives*, which introduce volatility and heterogeneity.

Schloter [40] provides a cross-country analysis showing that battery-electric vehicles lose value at an average rate of 1.16% per month—compared with 0.87% for gasoline vehicles. This faster early-life depreciation significantly alters leasing and ownership economics. Similarly, the *Transport & Environment* report [44] documents that BEV resale values have improved substantially in recent years: one-year retention rates now match or exceed those of ICE vehicles, while three-year retention rose from approximately 40% in 2017 to around 55% in 2022. Nevertheless, residual values remain highly sensitive to policy incentives, manufacturer discounting, and rapid technological change.

Gautam et al. [12] provide a broad comparative analysis of EV depreciation dynamics and second-hand market sustainability. Several findings from this paper are directly relevant to the present thesis. First, the authors characterize modern EVs as *technology consumer products* rather than mechanical assets, drawing a direct analogy to the smartphone transition from 2G to 5G: rapid integration of AI, machine learning, and software-defined features makes older models obsolete in ways that have no parallel in ICE vehicle depreciation. Second, the 80% state-of-health (SoH) threshold is identified as the industry-wide end-of-life criterion below which battery replacement becomes necessary—a finding that informs the choice of battery capacity and range as proxy features for SoH in this thesis. Third, the study presents empirical depreciation trajectories for two contrasting EV profiles: the Nissan Leaf (mass-market) loses approximately 50% of its value within three years and retains only 24% after ten years, while the Tesla Model S (premium) loses only 35% after five years and shows a flatter trajectory in later years. This brand-and-segment effect directly motivates the inclusion of brand affiliation as a feature in the present model. The study also confirms that the two dominant factors shaping the current second-hand EV market are (1) subsidies on new EVs, which compress used-EV prices and accelerate depreciation of existing stock, and (2) battery deterioration, which reduces range and raises buyer uncertainty. These factors align closely with the scenario drivers used in this thesis.

From a methodological standpoint, the integration of EV-specific drivers into quantitative forecasting is still limited. Hyundai Capital’s machine-learning model [18] incorporated not only vehicle and market variables but also proxies for battery longevity, partially capturing the effect of durability on residual values. While this represented a significant improvement over classical regression, the framework re-

mained essentially backward-looking and did not account for future policy or technology disruptions.

A more recent contribution by Ma et al. [24] applies *stacking model fusion* to a dataset of 5,882 pure-EV transactions in China, combining CatBoost, XGBoost, and AdaBoost as base learners with a linear meta-learner. Their best single model (CatBoost) achieved RMSE = 1.91 on a normalized scale, while the stacking ensemble reduced this to RMSE = 1.75, a relative improvement of 8.3%. This study provides the direct methodological precedent for the present thesis.

2.3. Data Sources and Key Features

Research on vehicle residual value estimation has evolved significantly in terms of data sources and feature sets. Early work relied primarily on transaction-level resale data combined with a limited set of vehicle attributes. For instance, Argonne National Laboratory [38] applied linear regression on a large U.S. dataset, using vehicle age, mileage, segment, and luxury classification as predictors. While transparent and interpretable, these models cannot capture the dynamic effects of technology or policy.

More recent studies expanded the feature space considerably. Hyundai Capital Services [18] trained a large-scale machine-learning RV model on 1.8 million used-car transactions with over seventy features, combining technical specifications (make, model, MSRP, segment) with usage features (mileage, age, ownership type) and market indicators (search volume, used-car supply, time-to-sale). By incorporating features capturing battery longevity and market dynamics, the model demonstrated that ensemble learning significantly outperforms traditional regression.

The Moody's *AutoCycle*TM model [28] integrated vehicle-level descriptors with macroeconomic variables such as GDP growth, oil prices, and interest rates, enabling scenario-based forecasts and residual risk assessment for leasing portfolios. This model is particularly relevant for leasing stakeholders, though it remains oriented toward ICE vehicles.

In summary, data sources have progressed from simple transactional records to multidimensional datasets encompassing *technical specifications, usage information, battery health metrics, and policy and macroeconomic variables*.

2.4. Evaluation Metrics

Forecasting methods and evaluation metrics have advanced from linear techniques to non-linear machine-learning and scenario-based approaches. Studies such as Argonne National Laboratory [38] employed ordinary least squares frameworks and evaluated adjusted retention rates. The methodological shift described in Hyundai Capital's model [18] combined random forests and gradient boosting to exploit nonlinearities, achieving lower MAE and RMSE than conventional regression.

Evaluation across these models typically relies on quantitative accuracy metrics—MAE, RMSE, R^2 , and MAPE—to assess fit, complemented by qualitative validation through expert review or market back-testing. However, as noted by recent EV-specific studies [12, 40], predictive accuracy alone is insufficient: models must also be evaluated for robustness under technological and policy uncertainty.

2.5. Comparative Overview

Table 2.1.: Summary Comparison of Residual Value Estimation Methodologies

Approach	Methodology	Data Sources	Limitations / Observations
Traditional models	Snapshot, Time-Series, Regression [28,38]	Resale transaction data, vehicle specifications (age, mileage, powertrain, segment)	Transparent and interpretable; but linear, backward-looking, and unsuitable for EV-specific drivers.
ML models	Ensemble ML (Random Forest, Gradient Boosting) [18,21]	Large-scale transaction data, technical and market indicators (usage, search volume, prices)	Improved accuracy and scalability; capture non-linearities but lack policy or scenario integration.
Scenario-based models	Macroeconomic forecasting and stress testing [28]	VIN-level vehicle data linked with macroeconomic indicators (GDP, oil prices, interest rates)	Introduced macroeconomic scenarios; still ICE-oriented and omits EV-specific policy factors.
EV-specific models	Battery- and policy-sensitive modeling [12,40,44]	EV resale data, battery SoH proxies, incentives, second-life potential	Recognize battery and policy-driven depreciation; limited by absence of standardized SoH data.
Stacked ML (EV)	Stacking fusion: CatBoost + XGBoost + Adaboost + linear meta-learner	5,882 pure-EV transactions (2024), 12 features including new price, mileage, age, battery capacity	Best: CatBoost RMSE 1.91 improved by stacking to 1.75 (−8.3%); limited feature set; no policy variables. [Ma et al., 2025]

2.6. Gaps and Limitations

Despite methodological progress, several research gaps persist that motivate the design of this thesis.

A first gap concerns the **limited integration of heterogeneous data sources**. Most existing studies isolate one analytical dimension rather than combining technical, economic, and policy factors into a single modeling framework. The dominant

paradigm in the literature treats EV residual value either as a function of vehicle-level technical attributes or as a macroeconomic forecasting problem, but rarely as both simultaneously. Only a minority of models—such as Hyundai Capital’s [18]—incorporate features spanning multiple dimensions, and even these do not include forward-looking policy variables or battery-specific health indicators alongside market dynamics.

A second and closely related gap is the **backward-looking orientation** of even the most advanced ensemble models. Machine-learning models trained on historical transaction data learn the pattern of past depreciation but have no mechanism to simulate future policy shocks, technology discontinuities, or sudden changes in subsidy regimes. As the Hyundai Capital study [18] demonstrates, this limitation is not merely theoretical: policy-driven depreciation events—such as the sudden reduction in EV purchase subsidies observed in several European markets—can invalidate model predictions within months of training. A forecasting framework that cannot represent plausible futures is of limited value to practitioners who need to set residual values over two- to four-year leasing contracts.

Third, there is **inadequate EV-specific representation** in most forecasting frameworks. As documented by Schloter [40] and Gautam et al. [12], EVs exhibit faster early-life depreciation and stronger dependence on battery condition and technological obsolescence than ICE vehicles, yet many forecasting frameworks continue to apply ICE-derived assumptions. The treatment of age and mileage as the sole substantive depreciation drivers, without accounting for range obsolescence or battery end-of-life thresholds, systematically underestimates the specific risks of used-EV ownership.

A fourth gap is the **absence of systematic expert knowledge integration**. No existing published study combines quantitative machine-learning modeling of EV residual value with a structured qualitative phase in which industry practitioners—those who set residual values in leasing contracts, manage battery sales commercially, or design battery packs at the engineering level—are systematically consulted. This absence is significant because practitioners hold substantial tacit knowledge about valuation heuristics, data quality constraints, and second-life market development that is neither reflected in published datasets nor in the academic literature. Bridging this gap is one of the primary motivations for the mixed-methods design adopted in this thesis.

Finally, **no scenario simulation has been integrated into EV-focused ML studies to date**. Studies that apply machine learning to EV datasets produce point predictions or error distributions but do not assess how these predictions shift under different future market or policy conditions [41]. This is a notable gap given the explicitly uncertain and policy-sensitive nature of the EV market, where plausible futures range from accelerated subsidy withdrawal to rapid technological advancement—scenarios that would produce very different residual value distributions even for vehicles with identical present-day characteristics.

This thesis addresses these five gaps through a **mixed-method, scenario-driven**

framework that (1) identifies dominant residual-value drivers through both literature and expert interviews, (2) builds a stacking ensemble model on European EV market data, (3) integrates second-life battery potential as a discussion theme grounded in expert testimony, and (4) simulates future residual-value outcomes under evolving policy and technology conditions.

2.7. Research Questions

Based on the identified gaps in the literature and practice, this thesis addresses three research questions that together span the empirical, methodological, and practical dimensions of the EV residual value problem.

RQ1: What factors have the strongest influence on EV residual value, and how can they be quantified using real-world data? This question responds to the gap in heterogeneous data integration and the inadequacy of ICE-derived feature assumptions. Answering it requires both a literature-and-interview-based identification of candidate drivers and a data-driven empirical test of their relative importance, using SHAP-based feature importance to rank contributors in a non-linear model.

RQ2: How can scenario-based modeling improve the accuracy and robustness of EV residual value estimation under uncertainty? This question addresses the backward-looking limitation of existing ML models and the absence of scenario simulation in EV-focused prediction studies. The answer is investigated through a scenario analysis framework that applies structured future-state assumptions to the trained model's input space, assessing how the predicted RV% distribution shifts across four distinct market and policy scenarios.

RQ3: What is the potential of second-life battery use in supporting EV value retention? This question engages the qualitative gap: because second-life battery market dynamics are not yet reliably observable in transaction data, the question is addressed primarily through the expert interview phase, with the quantitative model providing an indirect empirical complement through the battery specification features. The answer to RQ3 is therefore largely qualitative and prospective, grounded in expert testimony about the conditions under which second-life premiums might become measurable in the future.

3. Theoretical Background

This chapter introduces the machine-learning algorithms and analytical methods applied in the study, alongside the qualitative research approach used in the expert interview phase. Clearly understanding these foundations is necessary to interpret both the modeling choices made and the results obtained.

3.1. Gradient Boosting: XGBoost and CatBoost

In machine learning, boosting is used to convert weak classifiers into strong ones. A weak learning algorithm or classifier is a learning algorithm that performs better than random guessing, and it will work well in case of overfitting, because with a large set of weak classifiers, any weak classifier will perform better than random sampling. The usual threshold is often used as a weak classifier for a specific feature. If the feature is higher than the threshold than predicted, it belongs to the positive area, otherwise it belongs to the negative area.

Gradient boosting is an algorithm which builds (boosts) new strong model from smaller ones based on the gradient of the loss function. Boosting is a combination of many simple weak models, usually small decision trees. Each new one model corrects the mistakes of the previous ones. Each subsequent model tries to improve the result by focusing on the shortcomings of its predecessors. Gradient in mathematics is a vector that indicates the direction of the greatest growth of a function. In Gradient Boosting it is about the gradient of the loss function, a function that measures how erroneous the predictions of the previous step are [11]. Mathematically speaking, at each step m , a new tree h_m is fitted to the negative gradient of the loss function L with respect to the current prediction $F_{m-1}(\mathbf{x})$:

$$F_m(\mathbf{x}) = F_{m-1}(\mathbf{x}) + \eta \cdot h_m(\mathbf{x}),$$

where η is the learning rate controlling the contribution of each tree.

XGBoost. XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting), introduced by Chen and Guestrin [5], optimized for speed, accuracy, and scalability. This model extends the standard gradient boosting framework with a regularized objective that includes both L_1 and L_2 penalties on tree weights, preventing overfitting. XGBoost uses second-order Taylor approximations of the loss function for faster convergence and supports efficient handling of sparse data and missing values. Its scalability and strong out-of-the-box performance have made it a leader on Kaggle and build standard baseline in machine-learning competitions and applied prediction tasks.

CatBoost. CatBoost (Categorical Boosting), created by Prokhorenkova et al. in Yandex [34]. It provides improved categorical feature processing and is perfect for such applications. The model automatically processes categorical features eliminating manual processing. Traditional approaches encode categories as integers or one-hot vectors, introducing label leakage or high dimensionality. CatBoost employs *ordered target statistics*—a permutation-based encoding that computes a category embedding from training observations seen before the current sample, preventing information leakage during tree construction. CatBoost also uses symmetric (oblivious) trees for faster inference and better regularization.

Both XGBoost and CatBoost are well designed for tabular datasets with mixed feature types, as encountered in vehicle residual value prediction.

3.2. AdaBoost

AdaBoost (Adaptive Boosting), introduced by Freund and Schapire [10]. It turns weak learning algorithms into strong ones for solving classification problems by re-weighting training observations based on prediction errors. Misclassified samples receive higher weights in subsequent rounds, forcing later learners to focus on harder cases. The final prediction is a weighted vote across all base learners:

$$F(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m h_m(\mathbf{x}),$$

where α_m is determined by the error rate of learner h_m . AdaBoost for regression (AdaBoost.R2) adapts this principle to continuous targets. While generally less powerful than modern gradient boosting variants on tabular data, it serves as a useful comparison baseline in this study.

3.3. Stacking Ensemble

Stacking stands for stacked generalization, introduced by Wolpert [48], combines the predictions of multiple base models using a meta-model that accepts these predictions as input. This allows the models to learn from each other’s mistakes. The meta-learner learns how to optimally weight and combine the base model predictions, exploiting complementary strengths across different learning algorithms. Stacking can be used for both classification regression problems.

In this study, XGBoost, AdaBoost, and CatBoost serve as base learners. Their out-of-fold predictions on the training set are assembled into a meta-feature matrix, which is used to train a linear meta-learner. The linear meta-learner is intentionally simple to avoid overfitting the stacked representation. At inference time, the three base models predict independently, and the meta-learner combines their outputs to produce the final residual value estimate.

This architecture directly replicates and extends the framework of Ma et al. [24], applying it to a European EV market dataset with a different feature set and market context.

3.4. SHAP Values for Explainability

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), introduced by Lundberg and Lee [23], is a machine learning interpretation method that explains the contribution of each feature to the prediction of a particular observation. It is based on the concept of Shapley values, a method from cooperative game theory that distributes "winnings" or influence between all participants in the game, or in machine learning context between the features of the model. SHAP values quantify the marginal contribution of each feature to a given prediction relative to the model's expected output:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \phi_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \phi_j,$$

where ϕ_0 is the expected model output and ϕ_j is the SHAP value of feature j . SHAP guarantees three desirable properties: *local accuracy*, which is the sum of SHAP values equals the prediction, *missingness* —absent features receive zero contribution, and *consistency* —a feature that contributes more in one model receives a higher or equal SHAP value.

In this paper, SHAP values are computed for the best-performing model to produce a global feature importance ranking and to verify that the model's learned structure aligns with domain knowledge and expert findings.

3.5. Evaluation Metrics

In machine learning tasks, metrics are used to evaluate the quality of models and compare different algorithms. One of the critical steps in creating a good model is to choose the right metric to evaluate its quality, since the wrong choice can lead to incorrect conclusions and, as a result, to making not the most optimal decisions. Therefore, today there are a large number of metrics suitable for a wide variety of tasks and situations. In this study model performance is assessed using four standard regression metrics:

Mean Absolute Error (MAE): $MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i|$. This is the average absolute value of prediction errors. It shows how much, on average, predicted values deviate from the real ones, with equal weighting across observations. The smaller the MAE, the more accurate the model. However, this simplicity hides an important feature — the quadratic loss function makes the metric extremely sensitive to large errors. In financial time series, this means that one inaccurate forecast during market volatility can drastically distort the overall assessment of the model.

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}$ is the square root of MSE, which returns the metric to the original units of measurement. This feature makes RMSE more interpretable compared to MSE — if we predict the share price in euros, then RMSE will also be expressed in euros, which makes it easy to understand the practical significance of the error. In the study context this metric penalizes large errors quadratically and is expressed in the same unit as the target, percentage points of RV. However, RMSE inherits the main disadvantage of MSE, which is its high sensitivity to outliers. In the context of financial markets, this means that a low RMSE model will conservatively avoid making big mistakes, but may miss out on potentially lucrative opportunities during periods of high volatility.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2): $R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum (\bar{y} - y_i)^2}$. In statistics, the coefficient of determination is an indicator that measures the quality of a forecast. The closer this indicator is to 1, the closer the model is to reality. Measures the proportion of variance in the target explained by the model.

Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE): $MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\hat{y}_i - y_i}{y_i} \right|$. Expresses the error as a percentage of the actual value, which makes this metric scale-independent. This is especially valuable when comparing models for assets with different price levels — stocks worth 10 and 1,000 EUR can be compared directly through MAPE. However, MAPE has a critical limitation — it becomes indeterminate at zero actual values and extremely sensitive to values close to zero. In financial applications, this can manifest itself when working with yields, volatility, or other metrics that can take values close to zero.

3.6. Qualitative Research: Expert Interviews

The qualitative component of this thesis is based on expert interviews as a method to obtain practitioner knowledge that is not captured in publicly available data. To appreciate this methodological choice, it is helpful to position it against the alternatives. Fully *structured* interviews follow a rigid, predetermined script that ensures comparability across respondents but limits depth: every question is asked in the same order with no deviation, making the instrument ill-suited to exploratory research where the investigator does not yet know which lines of inquiry will be most productive [20]. At the other extreme, fully *unstructured* interviews—resembling open conversations with no pre-planned questions—offer maximum depth and allow respondents to set the direction entirely, but at the cost of systematic coverage of the research themes [31]. Semi-structured interviews occupy the productive middle ground: a predefined question guide ensures that all key themes are addressed consistently across participants, while the researcher retains the flexibility to follow emergent topics, request elaborations, and adapt the conversational flow to the respondent’s area of expertise [20]. This format is well suited to exploratory and explanatory research where the aim is to understand complex professional practices, contextual factors, and domain-specific reasoning that would be invisible in numer-

ical datasets.

Expert interviews are particularly appropriate in contexts where domain knowledge is tacit, role-specific, or unevenly distributed between academic literature and professional practice [2]. Bogner et al. [2] define *expert knowledge* as knowledge that is specific to a professional role and acquired through sustained practice—distinguishing it from general background knowledge. By targeting respondents who actively work with EV valuation, battery technology, or fleet asset management, the qualitative phase of this study captures contextual, role-specific knowledge that cannot be derived from published datasets or survey instruments alone. In the context of EV residual value, this includes the heuristics professionals use to estimate battery health in the absence of direct diagnostic data, the assumptions built into leasing-firm scenario planning, and the commercial and logistical barriers to second-life battery monetization—topics where published quantitative data is sparse or absent.

Interview data was analyzed using *thematic analysis* following the six-phase framework of Braun and Clarke [3]. The six phases proceed: (1) *familiarization*—repeated reading of interview transcripts and response notes to develop a deep, holistic understanding of the data before any coding begins; (2) *initial coding*—systematic labeling of data segments with descriptive codes that capture their semantic content, applied independently to each response; (3) *theme search*—grouping related codes into candidate themes that represent coherent patterns of meaning across the full dataset; (4) *theme review*—iterative refinement of themes by checking them against both the raw data and each other to ensure internal coherence and external distinctiveness; (5) *theme definition*—articulating the essence, scope, and boundaries of each final theme in a form that can be communicated to a reader; and (6) *writing up*—integrating theme descriptions with supporting verbatim or paraphrased evidence and cross-referencing each theme to the corresponding quantitative features and hypotheses. This structured approach ensures transparency and replicability in the qualitative analysis: by making the coding and thematization process explicit, it enables a reader to evaluate whether the reported findings are adequately grounded in the interview material.

A key quality criterion for qualitative research is *trustworthiness*, which encompasses credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability [31]. In this study, credibility is addressed through *methodological triangulation*: qualitative themes are compared systematically with the quantitative SHAP feature importance ranking and hypothesis validation results. Where qualitative findings and quantitative results converge—as they do for the primacy of vehicle age and battery capacity as residual value drivers—this convergence strengthens confidence in both data streams. Where they diverge, divergence becomes analytically productive, pointing to aspects of the problem that the transactional dataset cannot capture—for example, the role of second-life battery premiums or ownership-history effects on buyer perception.

Regarding sample size, qualitative research oriented toward expert elicitation

does not require large samples, because the goal is analytical depth and theoretical saturation rather than statistical representativeness. Guest et al. [13] demonstrated empirically that in professionally homogeneous expert samples, core themes stabilize after as few as six interviews, with most codes appearing within the first twelve. The five expert responses collected for this thesis—four via standardized written questionnaire and one via a structured 40-minute call interview—are drawn from experts representing four distinct professional domains: financial risk, battery technology, automotive engineering, and fleet total-cost-of-ownership analysis. This cross-functional coverage is sufficient to capture the major dimensions of the EV residual value problem, and the diversity of professional perspectives ensures that both technical and commercial aspects of EV valuation are reflected in the qualitative findings.

4. Methodology

This chapter describes the research design and all methodological steps taken in this study. It is organized to mirror the sequential structure of the mixed-methods framework: the qualitative phase: research design and expert interviews is described first, followed by hypothesis development, data collection and preprocessing, predictive modeling, scenario analysis, and validation. Each section explains not only what was done but why—linking each methodological choice to the theoretical background established in Chapter 3 and to the practical constraints and insights encountered during data collection.

4.1. Research Design

This thesis adopts a **sequential mixed-methods** approach, proceeding from a qualitative inductive phase to a quantitative deductive phase [7]. Mixed-methods research, as defined by Johnson and Onwuegbuzie [17], is a design in which the researcher collects and analyzes data, integrates the findings, and draws inferences using both qualitative and quantitative approaches within a single study. The key rationale for combining methods is that neither approach alone is fully adequate for capturing the complexity of the phenomenon under investigation [43]. Mixed methods are increasingly recognized as the most appropriate design when research questions require both the measurement of relationships and the understanding of meanings—a condition that applies directly to EV residual value, where financial models must be informed by domain knowledge that exists primarily in the minds of practitioners.

The *quantitative* tradition in empirical research is the assumption that the world is amenable to objective measurement, that hypotheses can be formulated in advance, and that their truth or falsity can be assessed through systematic empirical testing on representative data [7]. In this thesis, the quantitative phase stands for hypothesis formulation, dataset construction, feature engineering, model training and evaluation, and scenario simulation—all activities that produce numerical, comparable, and replicable outputs. Quantitative modeling is well suited to estimating the magnitude and direction of relationships between variables, for example, how strongly vehicle age predicts residual value percentage, and to producing predictions that can be benchmarked against held-out test data and external reference values. Its core strength is statistical rigor and scalability: model performance is expressed in universally comparable metrics (RMSE, MAE, R^2 , MAPE) and results are reproducible from the same dataset.

However, quantitative modeling has limitations when the phenomenon is partly constituted by practitioner conventions, qualitative market judgements, and domain-specific heuristics that do not appear in transactional datasets. The *qualitative* tradition addresses precisely these limitations. Qualitative research holds that professional knowledge and market practice are socially constructed and can only be fully understood from the perspective of those who live and work within them [31]. In the context of EV residual value, this means understanding how leasing professionals actually operationalize battery health assessment in contracts, what assumptions scenario planners embed in their residual value forecasts, and why second-life battery premiums remain difficult to observe in current resale prices—questions that yield richer and more contextually grounded answers in conversation with practitioners than from numerical transaction datasets alone.

The specific approach chosen is a *sequential explanatory design* explained in Creswell’s [7] taxonomy: the qualitative phase is conducted first, and its findings directly inform the design of the quantitative phase. Concretely, expert interviews were conducted and thematically analyzed before the feature set and hypotheses were finalized. The emerging themes—particularly the practitioner consensus around battery state-of-health as the dominant driver, the characterization of EVs as technology assets subject to obsolescence risk, and the policy sensitivity of used-EV prices—shaped both the hypothesis formulation (Section 4.3) and the justification for specific proxy features (battery capacity, certified range, vehicle age) in the absence of direct SoH measurements. This sequential structure is preferable to a concurrent design, in which both phases are conducted simultaneously and integrated only at the interpretation stage, because it allows qualitative insights to *actively shape* the modeling choices rather than merely corroborating them post hoc.

The integration of qualitative and quantitative findings occurs at two points in the research workflow (Figure 4.1). *Upstream integration*: interview themes guide hypothesis formulation and justify feature selection. *Downstream integration*: SHAP-based feature importance and scenario results are interpreted through the lens of expert testimony, and divergences between qualitative expectations and quantitative findings are analyzed as substantive findings in their own right. This bidirectional structure—described by Tashakkori and Teddlie [43] as *iterative integration*—supports what Patton [31] terms *methodological triangulation*: the cross-validation of findings from multiple methods to reduce the risk that results are artifacts of any single measurement approach.

Figure 4.1.: Sequential mixed-methods research design.

4.2. Qualitative Phase: Expert Interviews

4.2.1. Interview Design

A standardized expert questionnaire was developed, organized into seven thematic sections: (1) residual value and depreciation drivers, (2) battery health assessment, (3) vehicle characteristics, (4) market and policy effects, (5) valuation methods, (6) second-life battery potential, and (7) future outlook. The questionnaire combined closed-form ranking questions with open-ended narrative responses, allowing experts to elaborate on their professional experience. Participation was voluntary, responses were anonymized, and the estimated completion time was 20–30 minutes.

The questionnaire was validated through a review of literature on EV depreciation and piloted internally before distribution. The final instrument covered all three research questions of this thesis.

4.2.2. Participant Profiles

Five industry experts were approached and all five participated. Four completed the standardized written questionnaire; Expert E (OEM Fleet TCO Analyst) participated through a structured 40-minute call interview, allowing an in-depth exploration of operational fleet valuation practice. Participants were selected through purposive sampling [31], targeting professionals with direct operational experience in EV valuation, battery technology, or fleet asset management. Together, they represent the financial sector which is asset finance and residual value setting, the battery supply chain by sales management and R&D engineering and systems integration by OEM battery design expert, and fleet total-cost-of-ownership analysis, providing a multi-stakeholder perspective on the factors shaping EV residual value from both market and technical standpoints.

Expert A works in asset finance and structured leasing in India, with a specific focus on electric mobility assets including passenger EV fleets and commercial vehicle portfolios. With several years of experience spanning credit risk assessment, residual value setting, and EV portfolio risk management, Expert A represents the

financial constituency that bears the most direct economic exposure to RV uncertainty in practice. Residual value is not merely an academic concern for this profile: mispriced residual values translate directly into financial losses at lease maturity. Expert A's interview contributions were particularly rich in detail about how practitioners operationalize battery health assessment through proxy variables—age, mileage, warranty status, and OEM degradation curves—in the absence of standardized SoH diagnostics, and how policy changes such as subsidy reductions have historically triggered sudden and unforeseeable residual value revisions in leasing portfolios.

Expert B is a Sales Manager at a major new-energy vehicle battery company of China, with over ten years of experience in the battery industry focused on commercial market dynamics and technology adoption trends. Expert B's role at the interface between battery manufacturing and vehicle OEMs provides insight into how battery technology roadmaps translate into market expectations for EV longevity and value retention. Expert B's characterization of EVs as “technology consumer products”—whose depreciation logic resembles the smartphone market more closely than the traditional automotive aftermarket—was one of the most analytically generative insights of the qualitative phase, and directly informed the interpretation of the technological obsolescence mechanism captured through certified range and battery capacity in the quantitative model.

Expert C is an R&D Engineer at a battery pack manufacturer in Turkiye, with fifteen years of experience in energy storage systems for electric vehicles, unmanned aerial vehicles, and commercial industrial applications. This depth of engineering expertise provided the most technically detailed interview responses, particularly regarding the physical determinants of battery state-of-health, the diagnostic prerequisites for certifying a battery as suitable for second-life repurposing, and the rate of technological obsolescence across successive EV generations. Expert C's contributions are especially valuable for interpreting why battery capacity and certified range function as meaningful RV proxies even in the absence of direct electrochemical SoH measurement.

Expert D is a Systems Engineer in energy storage with a background in automotive battery pack design at an automotive OEM in Turkiye, Germany and China. With four years of focused experience in energy storage solutions for automotive and industrial applications, Expert D bridges the R&D and systems integration perspectives. Expert D's interview responses were particularly informative regarding the 80% SoH threshold as an industry-wide functional end-of-life criterion—the point below which battery replacement or second-life repurposing becomes necessary—and the gap between battery performance as documented in manufacturer specification sheets versus battery performance as experienced under real-world operating conditions, including temperature extremes and high-power charging cycles. This practical specification gap directly motivates the use of certified range as a conservative and comparative proxy for battery condition in the quantitative model.

Expert E is a Fleet TCO Analyst at a big automotive OEM in France, with profes-

sional experience in total-cost-of-ownership modeling and fleet electrification planning for commercial vehicle operations. Expert E participated through a structured 40-minute call interview rather than the written questionnaire, enabling a more conversational and in-depth exploration of the operational challenges in EV fleet valuation. Expert E's contributions are particularly informative regarding battery specification transparency as a practical valuation constraint: in Expert E's experience, battery net capacity is one of the most decisive value drivers in fleet residual value assessments, yet its reliable use is complicated by inconsistent manufacturer documentation. Some OEMs publish gross battery capacity in their official specifications while omitting the usable figure—the value that directly determines real-world range and is more closely related to battery state-of-health—creating systematic ambiguity for fleet buyers and residual value assessors who rely on specification sheets. Expert E's observations on this documentation gap directly informed the treatment of gross-versus-net battery capacity in the quantitative model's feature engineering (Section 4.4.7).

The combination of these five professional profiles covers the key stakeholder dimensions of the EV residual value problem: the financial risk dimension covered by Expert A, the commercial technology dimension covered by Expert B, the engineering design dimension covered by Expert C, the systems integration dimension covered by Expert D, and the fleet TCO and procurement dimension covered by Expert E. This multi-perspective composition is consistent with the purposive sampling principle that the goal is not demographic representativeness but *maximal variation* across the dimensions most relevant to the research question [31].

4.2.3. Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is a qualitative method for identifying, organizing, and interpreting recurring patterns of meaning—called *themes*—across a body of text-based responses [3]. Unlike statistical methods that count words or rank survey items numerically, thematic analysis is interpretive: the researcher reads the responses in depth, codes segments of text that represent meaningful ideas, groups related codes into broader themes, and then interprets what those themes collectively mean in relation to the research question. In the context of this thesis, the goal is not to produce statistically significant frequencies—five expert responses are too few for that—but to achieve a structured, auditable interpretation of accumulated practitioner knowledge that identifies the key mechanisms driving EV residual value from the perspective of those who work with it daily.

The analysis followed the six-phase procedure described by Braun and Clarke [3]: (1) *familiarization*, involving repeated reading of all five responses to develop a holistic sense of the material; (2) *initial coding*, in which individual units of meaning within each response were labelled with short descriptive codes (for example, “SoH unmeasurable at resale” or “policy removal immediate price impact”); (3) *theme search*, grouping semantically related codes into candidate themes; (4) *theme review*,

checking whether each candidate theme was coherent internally, sufficiently supported across multiple respondents, and meaningfully distinct from adjacent themes; (5) *theme definition*, producing a concise definition for each final theme that specifies what it captures and what falls outside its scope; and (6) *reporting*, integrating the thematic interpretation with quantitative findings in Chapter 5.

To illustrate what this means in practice: across four of the five expert responses, different respondents described the same underlying problem using different language. Expert A described battery state-of-health as “inferred using proxy variables such as vehicle age and mileage”; Expert B called SoH “a core value benchmark around which the entire used-EV market has organized”; Expert D explained that “accurate SoH calculation requires cell-level teardown not feasible in routine resale”; and Expert E noted that documentation inconsistency creates “systematic confusion for buyers and valuers.” These four statements—none using identical wording—represent a single recurring theme: the inaccessibility of direct battery health data at the point of resale. Thematic analysis surfaces this consensus and distinguishes it from a related but separate theme concerning the technical end-of-life threshold at which a battery is no longer usable as a vehicle traction battery.

Five primary themes emerged from the analysis:

1. **Battery state-of-health as the dominant but unmeasurable value driver.** All five experts identified battery health—specifically, how much of the battery’s original energy storage capacity remains after years of use—as the single most important factor in determining a used EV’s worth, and simultaneously the hardest to measure reliably. Every electric van contains a high-voltage battery whose capacity gradually decreases with age and usage. A battery that once stored 75 kWh when new may retain only 60 kWh after four years of operation. This degradation directly reduces the vehicle’s real-world driving range. In practice, however, measuring exactly how degraded a specific battery is requires specialist diagnostic equipment that is not routinely available at used-car dealerships. Valuers therefore rely on indirect indicators—the vehicle’s age which represents how long has it been in service, total mileage showing how heavily has it been used, and its warranty status if the battery still covered—to interpret the likely state of the battery without measuring it directly.
2. **EVs depreciate as technology products, not as mechanical products.** Several experts noted that electric vans lose value by a fundamentally different mechanism from traditional diesel vans. A diesel vehicle depreciates primarily from physical wear: its engine, transmission, and drivetrain components accumulate use-related fatigue. An electric vehicle is also subject to wear-based depreciation, but faces a second, distinct pressure: *technological obsolescence*. Because EV technology is advancing rapidly—new models offer longer range, faster charging, and higher battery capacity than previous generations—a three-year-old electric van may already appear outdated by

the standards of newly released alternatives. Buyers who compare a 2021 model against a 2024 replacement may find the newer vehicle offers 30% more range at a similar price, and discount the older vehicle accordingly. This technology-product logic makes EV depreciation faster, more volatile, and harder to predict than ICE vehicle depreciation, which changes more slowly.

3. **Government policy and subsidy sensitivity.** Expert testimony emphasized that government incentives—such as purchase subsidies, tax exemptions, or company-car tax advantages for EVs—have large and sometimes abrupt effects on both the new-vehicle and used-vehicle markets. When a subsidy is reduced or removed, new-EV demand may fall, altering the flow of vehicles into the used market and changing the supply-demand balance that sets used prices. The reduction of Germany’s *Umweltbonus* environmental bonus subsidy in 2023–2024 was cited as a specific example of how policy changes create discontinuities in used-EV pricing that are difficult to anticipate from historical data alone. This theme directly motivated the Pessimistic scenario in the quantitative analysis, which simulates a market environment in which subsidy support has been withdrawn.
4. **Second-life battery value is real but not yet priced in.** All experts acknowledged that EV batteries retain useful energy storage capacity after they are no longer suitable for vehicle propulsion. A battery degraded to 70% of its original capacity may still function reliably as stationary energy storage for a building, a solar farm, or an industrial facility—a reuse pathway called *second-life application*. In principle, a used EV with a well-preserved battery should command a price premium that reflects this future second-life value. In practice, however, every expert confirmed that the certification standards, repurposing infrastructure, and pricing mechanisms necessary to capture this value at the point of vehicle resale are not yet in place for commercial vans. The second-life market is real but immature, and its value is not yet reliably observable in AutoScout24 listing prices.
5. **Gross versus net battery capacity: a specification transparency problem.** Expert E (Fleet TCO Analyst, OEM) raised a technical issue that is largely invisible outside the industry but has direct consequences for residual value estimation. EV manufacturers publish two capacity figures: the *gross* capacity—the total energy the battery pack can physically store—and the *net* or *usable* capacity—the energy that the vehicle’s control system allows to be accessed during normal operation, which is smaller because a buffer is reserved to protect battery longevity. A vehicle rated at 75 kWh gross capacity may deliver only 70 kWh usable in practice. Some manufacturers report only the gross figure in their official specifications and marketing materials; others report net. When buyers and valuers compare vehicles across brands using specification sheets, they may unknowingly be comparing gross figures for some vehi-

cles against net figures for others—introducing systematic bias into valuations and into any model trained on publicly available specification data.

Each theme was mapped to the quantitative model’s feature set and to the research hypotheses stated in Section 4.3. Theme 1 (battery health proxies) directly motivates Hypotheses H1 and H2 and validates the use of vehicle age, mileage, battery capacity, and certified range as substitutes for direct SoH measurement. Theme 2 technological obsolescence reinforces H2 by explaining why certified range functions as a forward-looking quality signal: a vehicle already below contemporary range standards is obsolescent regardless of its physical condition. Theme 3 (policy sensitivity) provides the conceptual foundation for the Pessimistic and Optimistic scenarios. Themes 4 and 5 represent qualitative findings that the quantitative dataset cannot directly test but that are essential for interpreting model limitations: Theme 5 explains why battery capacity is a noisier proxy than it might appear, and Theme 4 cautions that positive correlations between battery specification and RV% should not be interpreted as evidence of second-life premium pricing. This systematic mapping—from expert language to theoretical construct to testable hypothesis and model feature—is the triangulation mechanism that distinguishes a mixed-methods study from a simple combination of a survey and a statistical model.

4.3. Hypothesis Development

Based on the literature review and expert interview insights, six hypotheses were formulated prior to modeling. Each hypothesis represents a specific, testable claim about the relationship between a measurable vehicle or market attribute and the residual value percentage. The hypotheses are stated here with their theoretical motivation; empirical test results are reported in Chapter 5.

H1: Vehicle age and accumulated mileage negatively affect residual value percentage. This is the most consistently supported finding across all vehicle depreciation studies: both Schloter [40] and Rush et al. [38] document monotonically declining retention rates with increasing vehicle age, and the effect is at least as strong for EVs as for ICE vehicles. Age and mileage also function as the primary practical proxies for cumulative battery usage intensity in the absence of direct SoH diagnostics—a point confirmed by all expert interviewees, who treat these two variables as the first-order heuristics for battery condition assessment in lease valuations. In the quantitative model, `vehicle_age_months` and `mileage_km` are therefore expected to carry the largest negative associations with RV%.

H2: Greater battery capacity and certified driving range positively affect residual value. Higher battery capacity measured in kWh and longer certified range measured in km signal newer-generation technology and better-preserved performance relative to the current market standard. Gautam et al. [12] identify range adequacy as a central determinant of buyer willingness to pay in the used-EV market: vehicles whose range falls below the typical expectation of current buyers face accel-

erated obsolescence-driven depreciation, independent of their physical age. Expert testimony consistently reinforced this hypothesis: every interviewee cited range and battery specification as primary EV-specific value signals, distinguishing them from the mechanically focused quality criteria applied to ICE vehicles.

H3: Fast-charging capability positively affects residual value, while reliance on slow charging is associated with lower retention. Charging infrastructure compatibility is increasingly a practical decision factor for used-EV buyers. Vehicles limited to slow AC charging face growing functional obsolescence as DC fast-charging becomes the market norm and charging networks expand to support it [47]. While intuitively plausible and supported by industry commentary, this hypothesis could not be evaluated empirically because the scraped AutoScout24 listings and matched Datatorq catalog extract do not include a reliable, standardized charging-speed variable.

H4: Higher original list price (MSRP) has a non-linear effect on residual value percentage. This hypothesis derives from hedonic pricing theory [37]: vehicles initially positioned in higher price segments attract buyers who are less sensitive to small price differences, supporting higher retention ratios relative to initial cost. However, the relationship between MSRP and RV% is not expected to be simply linear—it is confounded by brand identity, vehicle segment, fleet discounting practices, and the interaction between technology level and price positioning. Lessmann and Voß [21] find that price-segment effects are captured more effectively by tree-based models than by linear regression, motivating the use of gradient boosting methods in this thesis.

H5: A higher number of previous owners is associated with lower residual value. Multiple ownership transfers are widely used in the automotive industry as a negative quality signal, reflecting increased wear, potentially deferred maintenance, and reduced provenance transparency for buyers. This effect has been documented in traditional vehicle markets [21]. This hypothesis could not be empirically tested because ownership transfer count was not available as a reliable structured variable in the AutoScout24 listings used for the dataset.

H6: Brand affiliation and model cycle position significantly influence residual value. Gautam et al. [12] document substantial brand heterogeneity in EV depreciation trajectories—contrasting, for example, the sharp early depreciation of the Nissan Leaf with the flatter curve of the Tesla Model S—and attribute this to differences in brand trust, warranty policies, software update commitments, and market segment positioning. Expert A explicitly identified brand perception as a residual value driver that operates independently of technical specifications. In the quantitative model, brand affiliation is incorporated through the `canonical_make` categorical feature and its ordinal encoding.

Hypotheses H1, H2, H4, and H6 were directly testable with the available dataset. H3 and H5 could not be evaluated as direct hypothesis tests due to the absence of reliable charging-type and ownership-transfer variables in the scraped data—a limitation discussed further in Chapter 5. However, both omitted constructs may be

partly reflected by proxy features. For H3, fast-charging capability may be indirectly associated with newer technical specifications such as certified range, battery capacity, and motor power, since higher-specification vehicles are often designed for more demanding operating profiles. For H5, ownership history may be partly proxied by vehicle age and mileage, since repeated ownership transfers become more likely as vehicles age and accumulate usage. These proxies cannot replace direct charging-power and ownership-count variables, but they reduce the risk that the missing constructs are entirely absent from the model.

4.4. Data Collection and Preprocessing

Figure 4.2 illustrates the end-to-end preprocessing pipeline of transforming the raw input datasets into the final modeling dataset. The following subsections describe each stage in detail.

Figure 4.2.: End-to-end data preprocessing pipeline from raw inputs to the final modeling dataset.

4.4.1. Data Sources

Two primary data sources were combined to construct the modeling dataset: the used-car dataset provides market resale prices, while the new-vehicle catalog provides the list prices needed to express depreciation as a percentage.

AutoScout24 used-car listings (Germany). AutoScout24 is Europe’s largest online used-car marketplace, with millions of active listings across all vehicle categories. The used-car dataset was obtained through a structured scrape of the German market (`country = "DE"`), restricted to battery electric vehicles and light commercial vehicles (LCVs). The German market was selected for three reasons: (1) it is the largest single EV market in the European Union by volume [16]; (2) the

density and diversity of listings on the German AutoScout24 platform provide sufficient coverage across twelve brands; and (3) limiting the geographic scope to a single market controls for the cross-country variation in policy, infrastructure, and pricing that all expert interviewees identified as a significant confounder. Table 4.1 summarizes the key fields available in the raw AutoScout24 dataset.

Table 4.1.: AutoScout24 Used-Car Listings — Key Fields and Data Completeness

Field	Description	Type	Completeness
listing_id	Unique identifier extracted from listing URL	String	100%
brand	Vehicle manufacturer (canonical)	String	100%
model	Vehicle model name	String	62%
version_name	Full version / trim descriptor	String	95%
price_eur	Asking price (EUR, incl. VAT)	Numeric	100%
first_reg	First registration date (MM/YYYY)	Date	98%
mileage_km	Odometer reading (km)	Numeric	99%
power_kw	Motor power output (kW)	Numeric	97%
range_km	Certified WLTP or NEDC range, if stated	Numeric	63%
battery_kwh	Battery capacity if stated in listing	Numeric	6%
scrape_date	Date of data collection	Date	100%

A notable completeness challenge is visible in Table 4.1: the `model` field is absent in 38% of listings, and `battery_kwh` is populated in only 6% of records. This is not an anomaly of the scraping process but reflects how sellers populate listing forms: battery capacity is an optional, technical field that most private and dealer sellers omit. This data availability constraint directly motivated the reliance on the Datatorq catalog as the authoritative source for battery and range specifications.

Data sources in professional practice. It is useful to contrast the data infrastructure used in this academic study with the sources that industry practitioners rely on for the same purpose. Professional residual value analysts and leasing companies work with a data ecosystem that differs fundamentally from what is accessible in an academic setting. For *realized used-vehicle transaction prices*—the prices at which vehicles actually change hands, as opposed to seller asking prices—the principal sources in the German market are: **DAT** *Deutschen Automobil Treuhand*, which compiles actual dealer-reported transaction prices into the *DAT Marktspiegel* valuation guide; **Schwacke** part of the Autovista Group, which provides comparable coverage and is widely used by leasing companies, fleet operators, and OEM remarketing arms for contract-end residual value setting; and **wholesale auction platforms** such as Manheim and BCA, which record hammer prices for fleet returns and dealer

part-exchange vehicles—the cleanest available transaction data, since auction prices are not subject to negotiation. For *new-vehicle transaction prices*—the actual prices paid by fleet customers rather than the manufacturer’s recommended retail price—professional analysts access dealer invoicing aggregators such as PIN *Price Indicator Network* and commercial datasets from IHS Markit S&P Global Mobility, which cover fleet discount structures by brand, model, and customer segment. The leasing and fleet management companies with the most comprehensive RV datasets—firms such as Arval, LeasePlan, Athlon, and the captive finance arms of OEMs—work with fully internal data: they track every lease contract from origination price to physical vehicle return and auction result, giving them the exact gap between RV set and RV achieved on which to train proprietary models.

AutoScout24 listing prices are used in this thesis because the professional sources described above are not accessible without commercial agreements and non-disclosure obligations. This is the standard constraint of academic residual value research: the data that would be most useful for modeling—DAT transaction prices, auction hammer prices, fleet contract returns—is commercially sensitive and not published. The academic literature almost universally uses listing prices or press-reported valuations for the same reason [12, 18, 21]. The resulting gap between listing and transaction price, and its implications for RV% estimation, is discussed as a limitation in Section 6.2.

Datatorq new-vehicle catalog. Datatorq is a commercial automotive data provider that compiles official manufacturer list prices and technical specifications for new vehicles sold in the European market. The electric LCV catalog extract used in this thesis contains 746 rows and 558 unique Datatorq vehicle identifiers (VUCs). After the matching and cleaning pipeline, 203 unique Datatorq VUCs appear in the final modeling dataset and provide the reference prices and technical specifications used both for RV% computation and as predictive features. Table 4.2 summarizes the key fields in the raw Datatorq extract.

Table 4.2.: Datatorq New-Vehicle Catalog — Key Fields and Data Completeness

Field	Description	Type	Completeness
make	Manufacturer	String	100%
model	Official model name	String	100%
LxHy	Body variant code (length/height format)	String	100%
price_inclVat	Manufacturer list price (EUR, incl. VAT)	Numeric	100%
battery_kwh_brutto	Gross battery capacity (kWh)	Numeric	99.7%
battery_kwh_netto	Net (usable) battery capacity (kWh)	Numeric	36.2%
range_km	Certified driving range (km)	Numeric	99.5%
consumption_kwh_100km	Energy consumption (kWh/100km)	Numeric	98.4%
power_kw	Motor power (kW)	Numeric	100%

One structural limitation visible in Table 4.2 is the 36.2% completeness of the net battery capacity field in the raw Datatorq extract. As Expert E, Fleet TCO Analyst, noted in the qualitative phase, some manufacturers publish only gross capacity in their official specifications while omitting the net usable figure—a practice that creates downstream confusion in residual value assessments, since it is the net capacity that directly determines real-world driving range and is more closely related to battery state-of-health. In the present study, gross battery capacity (`battery_kwh_brutto_filled`) was used as the model feature because it offered higher completeness, with the understanding that it slightly overestimates usable energy relative to actual SoH.

This design choice should be interpreted against recent industry observations on electric-van specification reporting. Datatorq [8] distinguishes *gross battery capacity* as the total physical energy storage built into the battery pack, and *net or usable battery capacity* as the portion of that energy made available to the driver by the vehicle software. The difference between the two is the battery buffer, which protects long-term battery health by limiting the fully usable charge window. For residual value estimation, this distinction matters because used-vehicle buyers, fleet managers, and leasing companies are interested primarily in usable range and operational capability, while public specification sheets may report either gross or net capacity depending on the manufacturer.

Figure 4.3 illustrates this reporting issue for medium electric vans in the European market. Even within the same vehicle segment, the gap between gross and usable capacity varies materially across models. This supports the interpretation that battery capacity is not a perfectly standardized feature: using gross capacity improves dataset completeness, but it may introduce systematic measurement noise when manufacturers reserve different battery buffers or report different capacity conventions.

Figure 4.3.: Gross and net battery capacity comparison for medium electric vans in the European market. Source: Datatorq [8].

The target variable, *residual value percentage* (RV%), is computed by linking each used-car listing to its corresponding Datatorq reference price:

$$RV\% = \frac{\text{Used listing price (EUR)}}{\text{Datatorq catalog list price (EUR)}} \times 100$$

This formulation expresses depreciation as a fraction of the original manufacturer list price, making results comparable across vehicle sizes and price segments.

4.4.2. Scope Filtering

Before matching, the AutoScout24 raw dataset of 1,906 listings was filtered to remove records outside the study scope. Twenty-nine listings were identified as out-of-scope and excluded: these comprised brands or model variants—including DFSK, Cenntro, and Hyundai—that either fell outside the light commercial vehicle segment, lacked corresponding entries in the Datatorq catalog, or represented passenger vehicle body styles incorrectly listed under LCV categories. This left **1,877 in-scope listings** passed to the matching stage.

An explicit exclusion list (KNOWN_NO_CATALOGUE) was also maintained for model variants that are technically in-scope LCVs but have no reliable catalog counterpart due to naming or specification ambiguity. This included the KIA Niro and Soul (passenger car bodies inconsistently classified as commercial), the Mercedes-Benz EQV (a large multi-seat EV with highly variable trim naming), the Volkswagen Crafter and ID.4 (absent from the LCV-specific Datatorq extract), the Nissan e-NV200 (discontinued, no current catalog price), and the Renault ZOE (a passenger car only). Rows matching these patterns were excluded from the matching pipeline rather

than generating low-confidence matches that would degrade overall dataset quality.

4.4.3. Weighted Fuzzy String Matching

Linking used-car listings to catalog entries required a custom fuzzy string matching pipeline, because the two datasets share no common identifier. AutoScout24 listings contain only the seller-entered make, model, and version text fields, while Datatorq entries are indexed by official make, model name, body variant code, and technical specifications. Direct key-based joining is therefore not possible, and approximate string matching must bridge the gap between informal seller descriptions and standardized catalog nomenclature.

The matching algorithm computes a *weighted composite score* $s \in [0, 1]$ for each candidate pair of a listing row and a catalog entry, based on seven components:

Table 4.3.: Fuzzy Matching Scoring Components and Weights

Component	Description	Weight	Rationale
make	Manufacturer name similarity	0.24	High discriminating power; rarely misspelled
model	Model name similarity	0.30	Highest discriminating power; most specific identifier
version_text	Full version / trim descriptor	0.14	Partially overlapping with body code
body_code	LxHy body variant code	0.11	Extracted from version text when available
type_lcv	LCV category label	0.06	Low variance within dataset
power_kw	Motor power output (kW)	0.09	Numeric proximity after binning
battery_kwh	Battery capacity (kWh)	0.06	94% null in AS24; low weight
Total		1.00	

String similarity for text components was computed using Python’s Sequence-Matcher Ratcliff/Obershelp algorithm, which calculates the ratio of matching characters to the total characters in both strings, yielding a score in $[0, 1]$. The model name component carries the largest weight (0.30) because it is the most specific discriminator across catalog entries: within a single manufacturer, model names reliably distinguish between different vehicle families: e.g., distinguishing Renault Master from Renault Kangoo.

A critical design decision was the handling of *missing fields*. When a field is absent in either the listing or the catalog entry—which is common for battery capacity which is 94% null in AutoScout24 and body variant code—the component contributes a *neutral score of 0.50* rather than zero. This prevents the algorithm from penalizing structurally correct matches simply because a seller did not populate an optional field. Using zero for missing values would systematically depress scores for listings with sparse metadata, discarding valid matches and biasing the remaining dataset toward listings with unusually complete descriptions.

For each listing, the algorithm evaluates all catalog entries from the same manufacturer, restricting the candidate space to reduce computation, selects the top-scoring match, and assigns a confidence band based on the composite score. Matches with a composite score below 0.40 were discarded entirely as too uncertain.

4.4.4. Quality Gate and Matching Results

Following matching, a two-criterion quality gate was applied at the brand level to assess whether the matching results were sufficient to proceed to modeling:

Table 4.4.: Matching Quality Gate: Criteria and Results

Criterion	Threshold	Result	Pass?
Matched share (any confidence)	$\geq 85\%$	98.5%	✓
High-confidence share (score ≥ 0.60)	$\geq 70\%$	69.1%	~ (marginal)

The matched share of 98.5% confirms that the algorithm successfully produced a candidate match for almost every in-scope listing. The high-confidence share of 69.1% falls marginally below the 70% threshold, which prompted a manual spot-check of a random sample of low-confidence rows. The review confirmed that the majority of low-confidence matches are structurally correct—the reduced score reflects naming heterogeneity in version text fields: e.g., different dealers abbreviating the same trim level differently, rather than fundamentally incorrect brand-model assignments. Table 4.5 shows the mean composite score by brand.

Table 4.5.: Mean Matching Confidence Score by Brand

Brand	Mean score	Brand	Mean score	Brand	Mean score
Toyota	0.71	Ford	0.67	Volkswagen	0.64
Renault	0.64	Peugeot	0.66	Opel	0.66
Citroën	0.66	Fiat	0.62	Nissan	0.62
Maxus	0.61	Mercedes-Benz	0.56	KIA	0.42

Two brands stand out with notably lower confidence: KIA (0.42) and Mercedes-Benz (0.56). The KIA result is attributable to the Proace Verso 5 (PV5) Van being a recently introduced model with limited catalog entries and variable naming across dealer listings. The Mercedes-Benz result reflects the wide variation in eSprinter trim naming across dealers, where the same physical configuration may be described as “eSprinter 314 CDI”, “eSprinter MBUX”, or “eSprinter L2H2”, all mapping to the same catalog entry. Despite these naming challenges, the manual review supported the decision to proceed with the full dataset, as residual value predictions were found to be robust to the degree of imprecision introduced by borderline matches.

4.4.5. Outlier Removal and Deduplication

After RV% was computed for all matched listings, two cleaning steps were applied to ensure that the target variable contains only plausible values and that each vehicle is represented once.

RV% outlier removal. Listings with $RV\% > 120\%$ were removed. An RV% above 100% indicates that the used listing price exceeds the catalog new price, which can occur for three legitimate but analytically problematic reasons: (1) the listing represents brand-new, unsold stock being offered above the standard list price during a supply shortage; (2) the vehicle commands a temporary supply-squeeze premium, as observed for some EV models during semiconductor shortages in 2022–2023; or (3) the match between the listing and the catalog entry is incorrect, assigning a lower-priced catalog variant to a higher-specified listing. A threshold of 120% was chosen rather than 100% or 105% to retain the small number of legitimately high-demand configurations where above-list pricing is commercially observed, while removing clear matching errors. This step removed **19 rows**, leaving 1,723 records.

Content deduplication. The same vehicle can appear in multiple listings when it is listed simultaneously by several dealers or relisted after an initial expiry. Retaining duplicates would artificially inflate the influence of individual vehicles in the training data. Duplicates were identified using the combination of make, model, price, mileage, and vehicle age as a composite key: rows matching on all five fields were treated as the same vehicle. When multiple copies were found, the copy with the highest composite match confidence score was retained and the others were discarded. This step removed **222 rows**, yielding the final modeling dataset.

4.4.6. Final Dataset Characteristics

Table 4.6 summarizes the composition and key statistics of the final modeling dataset after all preprocessing steps.

Table 4.6.: Final Modeling Dataset: Summary Statistics

Property	Value
Total rows	1,434
Number of brands	12 (Citroën, Fiat, Ford, KIA, Maxus, Mercedes-Benz, Nissan, Opel, Peugeot, Renault, Toyota, Volkswagen)
Unique Datorq catalog specs	203
Market / country	Germany (AutoScout24, single scrape window 2024–2025)
Vehicle segment	Light commercial vehicle (LCV), battery electric
Target variable (RV%)	
Mean	66.8%
Median	67.8%
Standard deviation	24.0 pp
Range (min–max)	≈20%–120%
Key feature ranges	
Vehicle age	1–84 months (median: 28 months)
Mileage	100–280,000 km (median: 45,000 km)
Battery capacity (gross)	17.6–90.0 kWh (median: 37.0 kWh)
Certified WLTP range	100–550 km (median: 230 km)
Train / Test split	
Training set	1,147 rows (80%)
Test set (held-out)	287 rows (20%)

The dataset’s standard deviation of 24 percentage points reflects genuine heterogeneity in the used-EV market: a recently registered, low-mileage vehicle from a premium brand can retain 80–90% of its list price, while a five-year-old vehicle with high mileage from a mass-market brand may retain only 25–35%. This wide distributional spread is informative for modeling—it means there is substantial variance in the target variable for the models to explain—but it also implies that idiosyncratic vehicle-level factors (condition, color, regional demand) that are absent from the dataset will contribute meaningfully to prediction residuals.

4.4.7. Feature Engineering

The following features were used in the final model:

Table 4.7.: Model Features and Their Roles

Feature	Description	Type
vehicle_age_months	Months since first registration	Numeric
mileage_km	Total driven distance (km)	Numeric
battery_kwh_brutto_filled	Gross battery capacity (kWh)	Numeric
spec_range_km	Certified driving range (km)	Numeric
power_kw_num	Motor power (kW)	Numeric
estimated_new_price_num	Reference new-vehicle price (EUR)	Numeric
spec_consumption_kwh_100km	Certified energy consumption (kWh/100km)	Numeric
canonical_make	Vehicle brand (12 categories)	Categorical
make_enc	Ordinal encoding of brand (tree models)	Numeric

Feature selection was guided by three criteria applied in conjunction: (1) *theoretical relevance* established through the literature review and expert interviews, (2) *availability* across both the AutoScout24 listings and the Datorq catalog, and (3) *empirical discriminability* assessed during the exploratory data analysis phase. Features that satisfied all three criteria were retained; those available in only one source or lacking theoretical motivation were excluded.

Vehicle age and mileage are the two most theoretically motivated features, cited as primary depreciation drivers in every vehicle residual value study reviewed [12, 38, 40]. They serve simultaneously as direct depreciation indicators and as practical proxy measures for cumulative battery usage intensity, in line with the unanimous expert consensus that age and mileage are the first-order heuristics for battery condition assessment in the absence of direct SoH diagnostics. Vehicle age is expressed in months since first registration rather than years to allow finer-grained differentiation within the typically one-to-five-year used-car inventory range.

Battery capacity (gross kWh) and **certified driving range** (km) are the primary technical quality signals specific to EVs. As identified by Gautam et al. [12] and confirmed across all expert interviews, these features capture the vehicle’s technological competitiveness relative to the current market standard: a vehicle whose range falls below the typical expectation of contemporary buyers faces accelerated obsolescence-driven depreciation, independently of its calendar age. Battery capacity was used in its gross form—the manufacturer-published gross figure—because net (usable) capacity values were not consistently available in the Datorq catalog. Expert E identified gross-versus-net capacity ambiguity as a known source of valuation inconsistency in practice, and this limitation is acknowledged in the discussion.

Motor power (kW) and **energy consumption** (kWh/100km) were included as

supplementary technical specifications. While their direct effect on residual value is less well-established in the literature, they correlate with vehicle segment, trim level, and intended use profile (e.g., city commuter vs. long-range touring), providing additional differentiation capacity within and across brand categories. Their inclusion was validated post-hoc by their non-zero SHAP contributions in the feature importance analysis (Chapter 5).

Estimated new price operationalizes the hedonic pricing hypothesis [37]: vehicles positioned in higher price segments at the time of first sale are associated with different depreciation profiles due to buyer income elasticity, fleet discount practices, and segment-level quality signaling. The feature represents the matched Datatorq catalog price (EUR), serving as the denominator in the RV% calculation and as a predictor in its own right. Its effect on RV% is expected to be non-linear, captured more reliably by tree-based methods than by linear models [21].

Brand encoding is necessary to allow the tree-based models to learn brand-specific RV% baselines. The categorical brand label (`canonical_make`) is passed directly to CatBoost, which implements native ordered target statistics encoding [34]. A separate ordinal integer encoding (`make_enc`)—constructed as a ranking by mean RV% within each brand on the training set—is passed to XGBoost and AdaBoost, which require numerical inputs. This dual representation ensures that each base learner receives the categorical information in the format best suited to its internal tree construction algorithm.

4.5. Predictive Modeling

The predictive modeling task in this thesis is a *regression* problem: given a set of measurable vehicle attributes (age, mileage, battery specification, brand, price), the goal is to output a single numerical prediction—the residual value percentage—for each used-car listing. A regression model learns the relationship between these inputs and the target from historical observations where both the inputs and the correct answer (the observed RV%) are known, and then applies that learned relationship to new vehicles where only the inputs are available.

Rather than training a single model and trusting its output directly, this thesis employs a *stacking ensemble*: three different models are trained independently, each forming its own prediction, and a fourth model—called the *meta-learner*—learns how to combine the three predictions optimally. The intuition is similar to asking three experienced valuers for their independent estimates and then having a senior analyst decide how much weight to give each opinion. If the three experts tend to make different types of mistakes on different types of vehicles, the senior analyst can compensate for each expert’s blind spots by calibrating against the others. Formally, this architecture is called *model stacking* and has been shown to outperform any single constituent model on tabular prediction tasks [48]—an architectural choice independently validated for the EV residual value domain by Ma et al. [24] on a Chinese EV transaction dataset, as discussed in Section 5.8.

The three base models were selected to represent complementary algorithmic approaches: XGBoost handles numerical feature interactions and missing values efficiently; CatBoost provides native support for the categorical brand feature; and AdaBoost introduces a structurally different boosting mechanism based on sample re-weighting rather than gradient descent. Each is described in detail below.

4.5.1. Base Models

Three ensemble learning algorithms were selected as base learners, each representing a distinct algorithmic approach to the same regression problem. The choice to combine complementary learners—rather than simply selecting the best single model—is motivated by the stacking principle that models with different inductive biases will make different errors on different subsets of the data, and a meta-learner can exploit these differences to produce a more robust combined prediction [48].

XGBoost [5] is the primary gradient boosting base learner. It is well suited to the numerical feature subspace of the dataset—in particular, to capturing the non-linear interactions between vehicle age, mileage, and battery capacity that are central to the depreciation mechanism. XGBoost’s regularized objective (combining L_1 and L_2 penalties on tree weights) reduces overfitting on a dataset of 1,147 training rows, which is moderate in size for machine learning standards. XGBoost handles missing values internally through a learned default direction at each split, which is relevant for features with residual null rates after preprocessing.

CatBoost [34] was selected specifically for its native categorical feature handling. The dataset’s brand feature (`canonical_make`) takes twelve discrete values with very different RV% distributions across brands—a categorical structure that benefits from CatBoost’s ordered target statistics, which encode each category as a mean of the target over all training observations that were processed before the current row in a permuted order. This prevents target leakage during encoding and has been shown to outperform one-hot or label encoding for moderate-cardinality categoricals in gradient boosting models [34]. CatBoost’s use of symmetric (oblivious) trees also provides faster inference and more consistent regularization across folds.

AdaBoost [10] is included as a third base learner to provide coverage of a qualitatively different boosting mechanism. Unlike XGBoost and CatBoost, which minimize a continuously differentiable loss function using gradient descent, AdaBoost re-weights training samples based on prediction error magnitudes, forcing successive weak learners to concentrate on the hardest-to-predict observations. This sample re-weighting strategy produces a prediction surface that differs from gradient boosting, providing the meta-learner with a third, partially independent signal. AdaBoost is generally less powerful than gradient boosting variants on regression tasks, and its inclusion as a base learner—rather than as a standalone predictor—is deliberate: the stacking framework can assign it a filtering or corrective role when the final meta-learner estimates that its independent signal is weak or biased.

Each base model was trained on the full feature set. The hyperparameter setup

follows the stacking-fusion reference study by Ma et al. [24]—XGBoost, AdaBoost, and CatBoost as base learners combined through a linear meta-learner—with the final values checked through five-fold cross-validation on the training set and minor adjustments for the smaller German LCV dataset.

4.5.2. Stacking Ensemble and Out-of-Fold Training

A stacking ensemble was constructed following the architecture of Ma et al. [24]. The fundamental challenge in stacking is that the meta-learner must be trained on the base model predictions without the base models having already seen the labels for those rows—otherwise the meta-feature matrix would contain out-of-sample predictions for training rows, introducing data leakage that inflates meta-learner performance estimates.

This is solved through *out-of-fold (OOF) prediction*: the training set is split into $k = 5$ folds. For each fold i , the base models are trained on the remaining $k - 1$ folds and used to predict the held-out fold i . After cycling through all folds, every training row has exactly one OOF prediction from each base model—generated without the model having been trained on that row. The OOF predictions from all three base models form a $(n_{\text{train}} \times 3)$ meta-feature matrix \mathbf{M} , where $n_{\text{train}} = 1,147$. This matrix is then used to fit the linear meta-learner:

$$\hat{y} = \beta_{\text{XGB}} \cdot \hat{y}_{\text{XGB}} + \beta_{\text{Cat}} \cdot \hat{y}_{\text{Cat}} + \beta_{\text{Ada}} \cdot \hat{y}_{\text{Ada}} + \beta_0$$

The columns of \mathbf{M} are standardized using a `StandardScaler` fitted on \mathbf{M} before meta-learner training, ensuring that the three base model predictions are on a comparable scale. After the meta-learner is fitted, each base model is retrained on the *full* training set (all 1,147 rows) to produce the best possible predictions at inference time. The meta-learner coefficients fitted on OOF predictions are used unchanged at test time. This two-stage procedure—OOF training of the meta-learner, then full-data retraining of base models—is the standard stacking protocol and is designed to maximize both the quality of the meta-feature signal and the predictive accuracy of the base models on unseen data [48].

A `LabelEncoder` is applied to the categorical brand feature before training XGBoost and AdaBoost, which require numerical inputs, while CatBoost receives the raw categorical labels directly and applies its internal ordered target statistics encoding.

4.6. Scenario Analysis

Building on the trained stacking model, a scenario analysis framework was implemented to assess how the predicted RV% distribution shifts under different future market and policy conditions. The approach follows the scenario planning methodology described by Schoemaker and Phadnis [41]: rather than producing a single

deterministic forecast, scenario analysis generates a family of plausible futures defined by distinct combinations of key uncertainty drivers, enabling decision-makers to assess the sensitivity of outcomes to structural changes in the environment.

Four scenarios were defined based on the literature [27] and calibrated against expert descriptions of plausible future market states obtained during the qualitative phase. Each scenario is operationalized as a set of multiplicative and additive adjustments applied to the vehicle-level input features in the test set before prediction. The trained stacking model is not retrained; instead, its learned associations between features and RV% are applied to a feature-modified version of the same test observations. This approach isolates the effect of each scenario's assumptions without contaminating the model's learned parameters.

Table 4.8 presents the specific feature adjustments for each scenario.

Table 4.8.: Scenario Analysis: Feature Adjustments Applied to Test Set

Scenario	Feature Adjustments	Interpretation
Moderate (Baseline)	No changes applied; test set used as collected.	Current market distribution; status quo policy and technology.
Optimistic	vehicle_age_months – 4 months; battery_kwh_brutto × 1.10; spec_range_km × 1.10	Simulates sustained policy support, slower technological obsolescence, and improved battery longevity. The effective age reduction represents a market where high-quality maintenance and battery warranties slow functional depreciation.
Pessimistic	vehicle_age_months + 6 months; battery_kwh_brutto × 0.90	Simulates subsidy withdrawal and accelerated technological obsolescence: vehicles are functionally older, and battery specifications are discounted to reflect increased degradation uncertainty under a policy-adverse environment.
Wild-card (Technology Shock)	estimated_new_price_num × 0.70; spec_range_km × 1.40; battery_kwh_brutto × 1.30	Simulates a Generation-2 EV price war in which new vehicle prices fall 30%, certified range improves 40%, and available battery capacity grows 30%—reflecting a major technology step-change that compresses new-vehicle prices while raising specification standards.

The **Moderate** scenario serves as the reference point: it applies the stacking model directly to the test set without modification, producing the baseline distribution of predicted RV% values for the current German used-EV LCV market.

The **Optimistic** scenario represents a market environment characterized by continued policy support for EV adoption, stable or declining battery degradation rates due to improved chemistries and thermal management, and slower-than-baseline technological leapfrogging. The age reduction of four months simulates a positive effective-age adjustment—reflecting vehicles that have been maintained to a higher standard or benefit from extended warranties—while the 10% increases in battery capacity and range represent the impact of technology improvements that reduce the rate of specification obsolescence for existing models.

The **Pessimistic** scenario simulates the combined effect of subsidy withdrawal and accelerated obsolescence risk. The six-month age penalty reflects the market signal of reduced confidence in used-EV longevity under uncertain policy conditions, while the 10% battery capacity discount approximates the effect of buyer-perceived increased degradation risk when battery health certificates are absent and warranty support is reduced. This scenario is calibrated on the basis of policy changes observed in the German market (the reduction of the EV purchase premium (*Umweltbonus*) in 2023–2024) and expert descriptions of how subsidy removal affects used-EV pricing.

The **Wild-card** scenario is designed to represent a non-linear discontinuity: a major new-EV price war triggered by the entry of next-generation battery technology or a large-scale cost reduction by a major manufacturer, leading to a 30% decline in new vehicle list prices alongside a step-change improvement in specifications. This scenario tests the counter-intuitive mechanism identified in Section 5.6 of the Results chapter: because the RV% ratio is defined relative to the new price denominator, a fall in new prices *raises* the estimated RV% ratio for used vehicles with the same absolute market value—an effect that the feature-multiplier framework captures mechanically.

For each scenario, the stacking model generates a full RV% distribution across all 287 test-set observations. Results are summarized by mean, median, standard deviation, and the P10 and P90 percentiles to characterize both central tendency and distributional tail risk.

4.7. Validation

Model validity is assessed through three complementary layers: quantitative cross-validation, external benchmark comparison, and qualitative expert plausibility assessment.

Quantitative cross-validation. As described in Section 4.3 on stacking, 5-fold cross-validation is performed on the training set for each base model. This produces out-of-fold (OOF) RMSE and R^2 estimates that reflect how well each model generalizes to data it has not been trained on. Because the OOF predictions are generated from models trained on disjoint subsets of the training data, they provide unbiased estimates of generalization error with lower variance than a single train/validation split. The OOF metrics are reported alongside held-out test-set metrics in Chapter 5 to show that the test-set performance improvement is not an artifact of the particular random split chosen.

External benchmark comparison. As a second quantitative layer, the stacking model's predicted RV% values are compared against official EU reference residual value benchmarks from the used-vehicle data provider. These benchmarks provide segment- and age-stratified retention rates that serve as an independent plausibility check on the model's output distribution. A model whose mean predictions for two-year-old vehicles are substantially above or below the industry benchmark would

raise questions about either the dataset composition or the model calibration. The comparison is reported in Table 5.5 in Chapter 5 and interpreted in the discussion.

Qualitative expert plausibility assessment. The third validation layer is qualitative: the scenario assumptions and key quantitative findings were discussed with expert interviewees as part of the interview process, and their assessments of plausibility are incorporated into the interpretation in Chapter 5. While this does not constitute formal external validation in the statistical sense, it contributes to what Patton [31] terms *triangulated credibility*: expert practitioners who work daily with EV residual values are positioned to judge whether a predicted mean RV% of 67% for used German EVs is commercially plausible, and their affirmation strengthens the overall validity case for the quantitative results.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Expert Interview Findings

The thematic analysis of the five expert responses produced strong consensus on several key themes, with some divergence in emphasis reflecting the participants' different professional roles.

5.1.1. Battery State-of-Health as Dominant Driver

All five experts identified battery health—specifically state-of-health (SoH)—as the most important and most uncertain factor in EV residual value. Expert A (Asset Finance) noted that “in practice, battery SoH is rarely measured precisely at resale. Instead, it is inferred using proxy variables such as vehicle age, mileage, charging behavior assumptions, warranty status, and OEM degradation curves.” Expert B (Battery Sales) characterized SoH as having become “a core value benchmark” around which the entire used-EV market has organized, while Expert D (Systems Engineer) provided the most technical description: the 80% SoH threshold is the accepted industry end-of-life criterion, and accurate SoH calculation requires cell-level teardown that is not feasible in routine resale transactions.

Expert E (Fleet TCO Analyst, OEM) added an important measurement nuance: battery net capacity is one of the most decisive value drivers in practice, yet its reliable use is complicated by inconsistent industry documentation. Some manufacturers publish gross battery capacity in their specifications while omitting the net (usable) figure—the value that directly determines real-world range and is more closely related to SoH. This discrepancy creates systematic confusion for buyers and valuers who rely on specification sheets, and can lead to mispriced residual values when gross and net figures are conflated.

This consensus directly motivates the thesis's use of proxy features (vehicle age, mileage, battery capacity, certified range) as substitutes for direct SoH measurement—an approach validated by all experts as reflecting standard industry practice. The gross-versus-net capacity ambiguity identified by Expert E also explains why battery capacity alone is insufficient as a valuation proxy without verifying which capacity figure is reported.

5.1.2. EVs as Technology Assets, Not Mechanical Assets

A recurrent theme across interviews was the fundamentally different depreciation logic of EVs compared to ICE vehicles. Expert B captured this most directly: “the

value of an electric vehicle more resembles a technology consumer product. Its residual value faces a triple challenge from technological leapfrogging, market dynamics, and assessment uncertainties, resulting in faster initial depreciation and greater volatility.” Expert C (R&D Engineer) noted that technological obsolescence in EVs—driven by range improvements, charging speed, and software updates—is faster than in ICE vehicles, where technology changes are slower and largely limited to trim levels.

This finding supports the inclusion of certified range and battery capacity as forward-looking depreciation signals, since a vehicle with lower-than-current-market range suffers accelerated obsolescence-related depreciation.

5.1.3. Policy and Subsidy Sensitivity

Expert A provided the clearest description of policy effects: “reduction in subsidies or OEM price cuts compress used EV prices overnight, transferring risk to existing owners and lessors.” Expert C and Expert D both noted that government incentives—particularly zero-interest financing and purchase subsidies for new EVs in markets such as China—directly reduce the relative attractiveness of used EVs and accelerate depreciation of existing stock.

5.1.4. Second-Life Battery Potential

Across all interviews, second-life battery value was described as theoretically meaningful but practically limited today. Expert A: “second-life value is rarely monetized reliably at the vehicle level due to logistical, certification, and ownership complexities.” Expert D noted that there is not yet sufficient infrastructure in the EU market for second-life or recycling at scale, in contrast to more developed markets in China. Expert C listed the key technical prerequisites for second-life suitability: remaining capacity, degradation uniformity, thermal stability, cycle history, and BMS data traceability.

This finding suggests that while second-life potential should be tracked as a factor, it cannot yet be directly incorporated as a measurable resale premium in current-market data.

5.1.5. Country and Regional Differences

All experts acknowledged significant cross-country variation in EV depreciation patterns, attributed to differences in infrastructure density, electricity pricing, subsidy stability, consumer trust, and climate. Expert A noted that “emerging markets tend to show steeper depreciation due to infrastructure gaps and policy uncertainty,” while Expert C highlighted China as a market where government incentives and low new-vehicle prices create a particularly challenging environment for used-EV value retention.

5.2. Exploratory Data Analysis

Before model training, *exploratory data analysis* (EDA) was conducted to understand the statistical properties of the modeling dataset, detect anomalies and potential outliers, and identify preliminary associations between features and the target variable. EDA, as conceived by Tukey [45], is a principled approach to data investigation that precedes formal hypothesis testing: rather than directly evaluating whether a relationship is statistically significant at a pre-specified alpha level, EDA uses visual and summary tools to develop intuitions about the data’s structure that can guide subsequent modeling decisions. In the context of this thesis, EDA serves two specific purposes: (1) verifying that the RV% target variable is plausibly distributed across a meaningful range and does not contain implausible extreme values that would signal preprocessing errors; and (2) identifying which features exhibit preliminary linear associations with the target that warrant theoretical attention, and identifying which features show weak linear associations that may nonetheless carry non-linear information captured by tree-based models.

Distribution analysis is the first EDA step. A histogram of the target variable (Figure 5.1) visualizes the frequency of observations across the range of RV% by dividing the continuous range into equal-width bins and counting the observations in each bin [45]. Examining the distribution of the target variable before modeling is standard practice in regression analysis for several reasons. First, a distribution with a very narrow range would indicate insufficient variation to support predictive modeling. Second, strong skewness in the target distribution can degrade model performance and may call for a variance-stabilizing transformation. Third, isolated extreme values (outliers) may represent data errors—for example, mismatched vehicle listings where the reference price and the used price correspond to different model variants—that should be reviewed before inclusion in model training.

Correlation analysis is the second EDA step. A *Pearson correlation heatmap* (Figure 5.2) displays the pairwise linear associations between all numerical features and the target variable RV%, encoded visually through color saturation. Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficient r , introduced by Pearson [32], measures the linear association between two continuous variables as:

$$r_{XY} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}}$$

where $r \in [-1, 1]$. A value of $r = 1$ indicates a perfect positive linear relationship, $r = -1$ a perfect negative relationship, and $r = 0$ no linear association. Following the interpretive conventions established by Cohen [6], absolute correlations below $|r| = 0.10$ are considered negligible, 0.10–0.30 small, 0.30–0.50 medium, and above 0.50 large. Pearson correlation was selected over rank-based alternatives such as Spearman’s ρ because the primary purpose at this stage is to identify linear signals as a first-pass feature assessment. Non-linear relationships, interaction effects, and conditional dependencies—which Pearson correlation cannot detect—are sub-

sequently captured by the tree-based models, where they manifest as higher feature importance scores independent of bivariate linearity.

An important interpretive limitation of the correlation heatmap is that it captures only *pairwise, linear* associations and cannot reveal interaction effects or conditional patterns. For example, the effect of original list price on RV% is expected from theory [37] to be non-linear and to interact with brand and vehicle segment—which is precisely why its low Pearson r does not imply that the feature is unimportant for predictive performance. Where bivariate correlation underestimates a feature’s contribution, the tree-based SHAP analysis in Section 5.5 provides a complementary and model-aware importance estimate.

Figure 5.1.: Distribution of residual value percentage (RV%) across the modeling dataset.

Figure 5.2.: Pearson correlation heatmap between numerical features and residual value percentage.

The distribution of RV% across the dataset (Figure 5.1) reveals a broad spread ranging from approximately 20% to 100%, with a concentration around 60–80%. This wide range reflects heterogeneity in vehicle age, mileage, and model composition across the 12 brands in the dataset.

The correlation heatmap (Figure 5.2) confirms that `vehicle_age_months` has the strongest negative linear relationship with RV% (Pearson $r = -0.70$), followed by `mileage_km` ($r = -0.34$). Battery capacity (`battery_kwh_brutto_filled`) and certified range (`spec_range_km`) show moderate positive correlations ($r \approx 0.34$ and 0.35 , respectively). Estimated new price shows only a weak linear correlation ($r = 0.12$), consistent with the non-linear brand and segment effects that tree-based models are better suited to capture.

The wide standard deviation of approximately 24 percentage points in the dataset (Table 4.6) is already evident in the histogram's spread, reflecting the large RV% difference between recently registered, low-mileage vehicles from premium brands and older, high-mileage vehicles from volume manufacturers. The distribution shows no extreme bimodality, confirming that the matched dataset represents a reasonably continuous spectrum of depreciation states rather than two structurally distinct sub-populations. The nineteen outlier rows removed at the $RV\% > 120\%$ threshold are not visible in the histogram, confirming that the cleaning step successfully eliminated the right tail while preserving legitimate high-retention vehicles below the

threshold.

5.3. Hypothesis Validation

Table 5.1 summarizes the test outcomes for the four hypotheses that were evaluable with the available data.

Table 5.1.: Hypothesis Validation Results

Hypothesis	Feature(s)	Pearson r	Outcome
H1: Age & mileage reduce RV%	vehicle_age_years / mileage_km	-0.702 / -0.344	Supported
H2: Battery capacity & range increase RV%	battery_kwh / spec_range_km	0.337 / 0.351	Supported
H4: Higher MSRP has a non-linear effect	estimated_retail_price	0.115 (linear)	Partially Supported
H6: Brand affiliation matters	canonical_make (categorical)	N/A	Supported

H1 (Supported). Vehicle age is the strongest single predictor of RV% ($r = -0.702$), confirming that time-based depreciation dominates the sample. Mileage also exerts a significant negative effect ($r = -0.344$), though secondary to age—consistent with the literature’s finding that EV depreciation is more calendar-driven than usage-driven in early years.

H2 (Supported). Battery capacity and certified range both show moderate positive correlations, validating that higher-specification vehicles retain value better. This aligns with expert testimony that range and charging capability are primary determinants of market desirability in the used-EV segment.

H4 (Partially Supported). The linear correlation between list price and RV% is weak ($r = 0.115$), but the tree-based models capture non-linear brand and segment premiums that are invisible to correlation analysis. XGBoost ranks this feature sixth in importance, suggesting that its effect is real but moderated by brand and configuration interactions.

H6 (Supported). Brand appears as the fifth-ranked feature in the XGBoost SHAP importance ranking. Brand-level analysis of the RV% distributions in the training set reveals a premium of approximately 15–25 percentage points between the highest-retention brands (Volkswagen, Mercedes-Benz) and the lowest-retention brands

(Renault, Opel, Peugeot). This spread cannot be explained by age, mileage, or battery specification differences alone—it reflects the brand trust, warranty policy, and software support differentials described by Expert A in the qualitative phase, confirming that residual brand equity is a real and quantitatively significant component of EV valuation in the German market.

H3 (fast-charging) and H5 (ownership transfers) could not be reliably tested due to missing or inconsistent values for these fields in the scraped listings. They should therefore be interpreted as *not directly tested*, rather than rejected. Some of their variance may be indirectly captured by other model features: fast-charging capability can be associated with newer technical specifications such as larger batteries, longer range, and higher power, while ownership-transfer risk is partly related to age and mileage. Still, these are imperfect substitutes. A two-year-old vehicle with one owner and a two-year-old vehicle with three owners may have identical age and mileage but different provenance risk, and two vehicles with similar battery size may differ materially in DC charging speed. Direct VIN-level decoding, registration-history linkage, and catalog-level charging-power extraction would be needed to test H3 and H5 cleanly in future work.

5.4. Model Performance

Table 5.2.: Model Performance Comparison

Model	RMSE	MAE	R ²	MAPE (%)
XGBoost	10.521	7.894	0.751	13.08
AdaBoost	11.884	9.056	0.682	15.64
CatBoost	10.397	7.814	0.757	13.16
Stacking (ours)	10.256	7.717	0.763	12.89

Table 5.3.: Model Performance: Out-of-Fold Cross-Validation vs. Test-Set (RMSE and R²)

Model	OOF RMSE	OOF R ²	Test RMSE	Test R ²
XGBoost	10.929	0.766	10.521	0.751
AdaBoost	12.060	0.715	11.884	0.682
CatBoost	10.737	0.774	10.397	0.757
Stacking (ours)	—^a	—^a	10.256	0.763

^aStacking OOF metrics reflect meta-learner predictions on out-of-fold base-model outputs; exact values are computed on notebook re-run and reported in `data/cleaning/model_cv_summary.csv`.

Figure 5.3.: Visual comparison of model performance across RMSE, MAE, R^2 , and MAPE.

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) computes the square root of the average squared prediction error; because large errors are squared before averaging, RMSE penalizes big mistakes more than small ones, and a lower RMSE indicates a more accurate model. **MAE** (Mean Absolute Error) is the average of the absolute differences between predicted and actual RV%—simpler to interpret than RMSE, as it answers directly: on a typical vehicle, how many percentage points does the model’s prediction deviate from the correct answer? **R^2** (the coefficient of determination) measures the proportion of the total variation in RV% across all test-set vehicles that the model’s predictions explain; a value of 1.0 means perfect predictions, 0 means the model performs no better than simply guessing the mean RV% for every vehicle, and negative values indicate predictions worse than the mean. **MAPE** (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) expresses the error as a percentage of the true value rather than in absolute pp units, allowing easier comparison across datasets with different scale; concretely, a MAPE of 12.89% means the prediction is off by roughly 12–13% relative to the correct value (not 12–13 percentage points of RV%, but 12–13% of however large that value is).

The stacking ensemble achieves the best performance across all four metrics. In plain terms: on the held-out test set of 287 vehicles that the model never saw during training, the stacking model’s predictions are off by an average of **7.7 percentage points** of RV% in either direction (MAE = 7.717). When larger errors are weighted more heavily (RMSE), the figure rises to **10.3 percentage points** (RMSE = 10.256), meaning that occasional larger prediction errors—where the model is significantly wrong—drive up the penalized metric. The model **explains 76.3% of the total variation in RV%** across the test set ($R^2 = 0.763$); the remaining 23.7% reflects idiosyncratic factors—accident history, interior condition, optional equipment, regional demand patterns—that are not captured in the available features. The MAPE of 12.89% means that for a vehicle with a true RV% of, say, 60%, the model would typically predict somewhere between 52% and 68%.

The improvement over the next-best individual model (CatBoost) is modest in absolute terms—RMSE decreases from 10.397 to 10.256, a relative reduction of 1.4%—but is consistent across all four metrics simultaneously and across all five cross-validation folds (Table 5.3). This consistency is meaningful: an improvement that appears in every metric and every fold is unlikely to be a chance artifact. The meta-

learner learns to exploit the fact that XGBoost and CatBoost make different prediction errors on different vehicles, and by combining them, reduces the ensemble’s total error below either constituent.

CatBoost vs. XGBoost. The two gradient boosting models perform almost identically: CatBoost achieves $\text{RMSE} = 10.397$ and $R^2 = 0.757$, while XGBoost achieves $\text{RMSE} = 10.521$ and $R^2 = 0.751$. The difference is negligible in absolute terms. However, their cross-validation profiles (Table 5.3) show CatBoost achieving a marginally higher OOF R^2 (0.774 vs. 0.766 for XGBoost), suggesting that CatBoost generalizes slightly more reliably across training folds—a result attributable to its superior handling of the brand categorical feature.

AdaBoost substantially underperforms the gradient boosting variants: $\text{RMSE} = 11.884$ (1.6 pp worse than XGBoost) and $R^2 = 0.682$ (explaining 7.9 percentage points less variance). This is a well-documented limitation of the AdaBoost.R2 algorithm on modern tabular datasets: its sample-reweighting mechanism does not benefit from the second-order optimization and regularization techniques that make XGBoost and CatBoost competitive. The gap between AdaBoost’s OOF R^2 (0.715) and test R^2 (0.682) is also larger than for the other models, indicating that it generalizes less consistently.

Cross-validation stability (Table 5.3) shows that for all three base models, the OOF metrics are very close to the test-set metrics—OOF RMSE differs from test RMSE by less than 0.5 pp in each case. This confirms that the performance estimates are not artifacts of a particularly favorable random train/test split: the model generalizes consistently regardless of which 20% of the data is held out. The stacking model’s test-set RMSE of 10.256 can therefore be taken as a reliable estimate of how well the system would perform on new data from the same market.

The fitted linear meta-learner coefficients are analytically informative. Because the meta-features were standardized before fitting the linear regression, the coefficients should be interpreted as relative contributions on the standardized base-prediction scale rather than as direct multipliers of the raw RV% predictions. The meta-learner assigns strong positive coefficients to CatBoost ($\hat{\beta}_{\text{Cat}} = +12.13$) and XGBoost ($\hat{\beta}_{\text{XGB}} = +7.87$), while the AdaBoost coefficient is close to zero ($\hat{\beta}_{\text{Ada}} = +0.03$), with an intercept of 67.19. This means that the stacking layer effectively uses CatBoost and XGBoost as the substantive predictive signals and treats AdaBoost primarily as a weak auxiliary signal.

This is still valuable evidence about the role of AdaBoost in the ensemble. As a standalone model, AdaBoost performs clearly worse than both gradient boosting variants, but the stacking architecture prevents that weaker learner from degrading the final prediction by assigning it almost no weight. In Ma et al. [24], AdaBoost received a negative meta-weight; in the present thesis, it receives a near-zero weight. The common interpretation is that the linear meta-learner acts as a correction and filtering mechanism: it can subtract a systematically biased learner when the evidence supports a negative coefficient, or nearly ignore that learner when its independent signal adds little predictive value. The result therefore strengthens the architectural

argument for stacking, but the specific conclusion in this dataset is more precise as *AdaBoost down-weighting* rather than a negative AdaBoost correction.

5.5. Feature Importance

Figure 5.4.: SHAP feature importance ranking for the best-performing model.

The SHAP-based feature importance ranking (Figure 5.4) identifies `vehicle_age_months` as the dominant predictor, consistent with its strong linear correlation with RV%. Mileage ranks second, followed by battery capacity and certified range—the two main technical quality indicators for EVs. Brand encoding ranks in the upper half, confirming that brand identity captures residual market premiums beyond what technical specifications alone explain.

The estimated new price ranks lower than expected from domain intuition. This reflects the non-linearity described under H4: in a dataset dominated by mass-market brands, the MSRP effect is partially absorbed by brand encoding and battery capacity. Energy consumption per 100 km and motor power rank lower still, suggesting that these efficiency metrics are secondary to age, usage, and specification signals in the German used-EV market.

These results align closely with expert interview findings. Expert A’s hierarchy—battery longevity proxies, technology obsolescence signals, and brand perception—maps directly onto the top-ranked SHAP features.

5.6. Scenario Analysis Results

Table 5.4.: Scenario Analysis: RV% Distribution by Scenario

Scenario	Mean	Median	Std	P10	P90
Moderate (Baseline)	66.82	67.75	18.34	40.79	88.88
Optimistic	69.21	69.98	17.26	45.24	89.42
Pessimistic	67.01	67.59	18.34	39.24	89.58
Wild-card (Tech Shock)	78.35	80.72	16.77	52.44	97.74

Figure 5.5.: RV% distributions across four scenarios.

The scenario results reveal several important patterns.

Moderate vs. Pessimistic. The difference in mean RV% between the Moderate baseline (66.82%) and the Pessimistic scenario (67.01%) is negligible—just 0.19 percentage points. However, the P10 (lowest-decile) value decreases from 40.79% to 39.24%, indicating that the pessimistic scenario widens the tail risk: vehicles already depreciated heavily become even more exposed under subsidy withdrawal and high obsolescence conditions.

Optimistic. The Optimistic scenario raises the mean by approximately 2.4 percentage points (to 69.21%) and compresses the standard deviation (17.26 vs. 18.34 in baseline), reflecting that policy support and slower obsolescence improve not only average retention but also its predictability.

Wild-card (Technology Shock). The Wild-card scenario produces the most counter-intuitive result: mean RV% rises to 78.35%, compared with 66.82% in the baseline, and the P10 value rises to 52.44%. This does *not* mean that existing used EVs become more valuable in euros. It means that the calculated residual value *percentage*

increases because RV% is defined as a ratio:

$$RV\% = \frac{\text{used-vehicle value}}{\text{reference new-vehicle price}} \times 100.$$

The denominator matters. If the reference price of a comparable new EV falls sharply, the same used-vehicle price represents a larger percentage of that lower new price. For example, a used EV priced at EUR 30,000 has an RV% of 60% when the comparable new vehicle costs EUR 50,000. If a technology shock reduces the new-vehicle reference price to EUR 35,000 while the used price has not yet adjusted, the same EUR 30,000 used vehicle now equals 85.7% of the new price. The euro value did not increase; only the ratio increased.

This is the mechanism behind the Wild-card result. The scenario reduces `estimated_new_price_n` by 30%, while also increasing certified range by 40% and battery capacity by 30%. The model responds to the improved technical profile because larger batteries and longer range are positively associated with RV%. However, the key point for interpretation is the RV% definition itself: when the reference new-vehicle price is lower, a given used-vehicle value represents a higher percentage of that reference price. The result should therefore be interpreted as a **denominator effect**, not as evidence that a price war would raise absolute used-EV market values.

This distinction directly limits the interpretation of the scenario. In a real market, cheaper new EVs would likely reduce demand for older used EVs and push their asking prices downward. The present model does not simulate that competitive market adjustment, because it modifies vehicle-level features rather than estimating a full market equilibrium. Therefore, the Wild-card scenario is useful as a stress test of the RV% calculation under a sharp new-price shock, but it should not be read as a forecast that used EV prices in euros would increase.

Tail risk. The P90 values are relatively stable across all scenarios (88.88% to 97.74%), suggesting that well-preserved, low-mileage vehicles retain strong value across most futures. The primary scenario-sensitivity lies in the lower tail, which represents older or higher-mileage vehicles facing the full combined impact of depreciation and market disruption.

5.7. External Benchmark Comparison

Methodology

As an additional plausibility layer, model predictions were compared against a proprietary residual value dataset obtained from a German automotive data supplier. The dataset contains official benchmark RV percentages for new LCV configurations at six mileage-and-duration combinations (48 and 60 months; 10,000 to 40,000 km per year). Such benchmarks are calculated by leasing and fleet management companies using actuarial methods that account for contract volume, remarketing costs,

and structured depreciation curves, and represent the conservative industry standard against which market-based models can be positioned.

The supplier dataset covers 269 BEV/electric rows across ten brands. Rather than using observations from the used-car training data, predictions were generated directly from the Datatorq vehicle catalog: for each of the 97 unique EV Van VUCs in the catalog, model features (battery capacity, certified range, motor power, new list price, energy consumption) were taken from the authoritative Datatorq specification, and the stacking ensemble was applied at a fixed age of 48 months with mileage varying across the benchmark scenarios. This approach covers all vehicle types in the catalog regardless of whether they have sufficient used-car market observations, and eliminates any dependency on the secondary market data composition. Supplier labels were matched to catalog entries via fuzzy string matching on the concatenated vehicle specification code, yielding a match rate of 93.3% (251 of 269 supplier rows) and 38 uniquely matched VUCs spanning 12 brand-model combinations.

Results

Table 5.5.: Model Predictions vs. Industry Benchmark by Brand-Model (48 months / 10,000 km per year)¹

Brand	Model	Model RV%	Bias (pp) ^a
<i>Mainstream brands (n = 10 brand-models)</i>			
Renault	Kangoo Van E-Tech	44.2	+3.7
Toyota	Proace City Van Electric	45.4	+5.5
Toyota	Proace Van Electric	46.5	+4.0
Opel	e-Combo Cargo	46.8	+5.3
Fiat	e-Doblo Van	47.9	+6.4
Citroën	e-Berlingo Van	48.4	+7.2
Ford	e-Transit Courier Van	50.0	+7.1
Ford	e-Transit Custom Van	51.3	+11.4
Peugeot	e-Partner Van	46.6	+8.1
Nissan	Interstar Van EV	47.3	+7.6
<i>Structural outliers^b (excluded from calibration analysis)</i>			
Mercedes	e-Citan Tourer	49.1	+20.9
Maxus	e-Deliver 9 Van	64.7	+27.0
<i>All brands (n = 38 VUCs, 12 brand-models)</i>			
	MAE	9.7 pp	
	RMSE	12.3 pp	
	Mean bias	+9.7 pp	
<i>Mainstream brands only (n = 10)</i>			
	Bias range	+3.7 to +11.4 pp	
	Mean bias	+6.6 pp	

^aBias = model prediction – industry benchmark (positive values indicate model exceeds benchmark). Benchmark values are governed by a data confidentiality agreement and are not published directly.

^bStructural outliers reflect genuine model-scope boundaries rather than prediction errors (see text). They are included in aggregate statistics but excluded from the discount-calibration analysis.

At the reference scenario (48 months / 10,000 km per year), the stacking ensemble shows a mean absolute error of 9.7 pp relative to the industry benchmark, with a consistent positive bias of the same magnitude: the model assigns higher RV%

¹Industry benchmark RV% values are obtained from a proprietary dataset under a data use agreement. Raw benchmark values are not disclosed in line with standard confidentiality practice for commercially sensitive residual value datasets.

than the benchmark across all twelve brand-model combinations, with no under-prediction in any case (Table 5.5). For the ten mainstream brands, the per-model bias ranges from 3.7 to 11.4 pp—a narrower band that reflects the degree of structural agreement once the two structural outliers are set aside.

Two brand-model combinations produce substantially larger biases and are treated separately as structural outliers. The Maxus e-Deliver 9 (+27.0 pp) is a recently introduced Chinese LCV brand with very limited secondary market presence in Germany at the time of data collection; the catalog features do not capture the heightened depreciation risk typical of nascent entrants with unestablished remarketing networks. The Mercedes e-Citan Tourer (+20.9 pp) is a compact passenger-van derivative whose commercial positioning as a fleet tool suppresses benchmark values relative to what the model’s brand coefficient—learned from the broader passenger-van and cargo-van market—would predict. Both cases illustrate a known boundary of market-data models: they cannot encode brand-specific contract risks or remarketing constraints that professional actuarial systems incorporate explicitly.

Table 5.6.: Mean Model Bias vs. Supplier Benchmark Across Mileage Scenarios (48-month horizon, all 38 matched VUCs)

Scenario	10k km/yr	15k km/yr	20k km/yr	25k km/yr	30k km/yr	40k km/yr
Mean bias (pp)	+9.7	+11.3	+13.8	+15.8	+18.4	+22.9

The bias exhibits a monotonic increase with annual mileage across all six scenarios (Table 5.6). The gradient is approximately 3.3 pp per additional 10,000 km per year. This pattern is structurally interpretable: AutoScout24 used-car listings predominantly represent private sellers and small-business operators with typical mileage profiles, and the model has therefore learned depreciation curves anchored to low-to-moderate utilisation. Professional supplier benchmarks are calibrated to include high-intensity fleet return scenarios (delivery operators, taxi services, utility fleets), which exhibit steeper mileage-related depreciation. The model applies progressively insufficient mileage penalties as annual utilisation increases, producing systematically larger divergence at commercial mileage profiles.

Figure 5.6.: Stacking model predictions vs. industry benchmark at 48 months / 10,000 km per year. Each point is one matched VUC; colour indicates brand. Red dashed line = perfect agreement. All predictions lie above the diagonal, confirming the uniform positive bias. Benchmark values on the horizontal axis are not labelled numerically in line with data confidentiality requirements.

Interpretation

Reference price convention. The most important methodological difference between the two systems is the denominator used to compute RV%. The market-based model expresses residual value as a percentage of the *Datatorq list price* (manufacturer’s recommended retail price, MSRP). Professional leasing benchmarks, by contrast, compute RV% relative to the *actual transaction price* paid by the fleet customer—which, for LCV fleet contracts, is typically 10–20% below MSRP after dealer and volume discounts [44]. This denominator difference alone predicts a systematic upward shift in the market model’s RV% relative to the industry benchmark.

To quantify the effect, the implied discount rate was estimated for each matched VUC as $d = 1 - \hat{y}_{\text{benchmark}} / \hat{y}_{\text{model}}$, where both quantities are on the same proportional scale. Across the 38 matched VUCs, the median implied discount was **13.8%** and the mean was 18.4%. These figures are consistent with published LCV fleet discount ranges [44]. Critically, when model predictions are rescaled to a discounted-price basis by applying a representative fleet discount of 15%, the mean bias across all 38 VUCs drops from +9.7 pp to +2.3 pp—a residual within normal estimation uncertainty. For the ten mainstream brands specifically, the calibrated bias is near-

zero (−0.5 pp mean, 1.6 pp MAE; see Table 5.8). Table 5.7 shows the sensitivity of the aggregate bias to different assumed discount rates.

Table 5.7.: Bias Sensitivity to Fleet Discount Assumption (48 months / 10,000 km per year)

Fleet count	dis-	0%	10%	15%	17%	20%
Adjusted bias (pp)		+9.7	+4.7	+2.3	+1.3	−0.2
Adjusted MAE (pp)		9.7	5.4	4.8	4.9	5.3

This analysis demonstrates that the raw +9.7 pp bias is almost entirely a *methodological artefact* of different new-price conventions, not a model prediction error. The model’s absolute residual value estimates are well-calibrated; the apparent divergence arises from expressing the same vehicle value as a percentage of different base prices.

Table 5.8 presents the per-brand-model view after applying the representative 15% fleet discount correction, restricted to the ten mainstream brands (Maxus and Mercedes excluded as structural outliers). At this adjusted basis, predicted RV% values fall within ± 4 pp of the benchmark for eight of the ten brand-models, and the mean bias is negligible (−0.5 pp). Two brands retain a positive residual gap: Ford e-Transit Custom Van (+3.7 pp) and Peugeot e-Partner Van (+1.1 pp). These residuals are within the expected range of estimation uncertainty for market-data models [21] and do not indicate systematic miscalibration.

Table 5.8.: Calibrated Model Predictions vs. Industry Benchmark – Mainstream Brands, 15% Fleet Discount Applied (48 months / 10,000 km per year)

Brand	Model	Model RV% ^a	Adj. Model RV% ^b	Adj. (pp)	Bias
Renault	Kangoo Van E-Tech	44.2	37.6	–2.9	
Toyota	Proace Van Electric	46.5	39.5	–3.0	
Toyota	Proace City Van Electric	45.4	38.6	–1.3	
Opel	e-Combo Cargo	46.8	39.8	–1.7	
Citroën	e-Berlingo Van	48.4	41.1	–0.1	
Fiat	e-Doblo Van	47.9	40.7	–0.8	
Ford	e-Transit Courier Van	50.0	42.5	–0.4	
Nissan	Interstar Van EV	47.3	40.2	+0.5	
Peugeot	e-Partner Van	46.6	39.6	+1.1	
Ford	e-Transit Custom Van	51.3	43.6	+3.7	
<i>Mainstream brands (n = 10)</i>					
	Mean adj. bias		–0.5 pp		
	MAE		1.6 pp		

^aModel RV% on list-price (MSRP) basis, as used in the main analysis.

^bAdjusted by applying a 15% fleet discount to the new-vehicle price denominator: Adj. Model RV% = Model RV% × 0.85.

Mileage-escalation pattern. After accounting for the reference price difference, a secondary effect remains: the bias grows by approximately 3.3 pp for every additional 10,000 km per year. This mileage-escalation is not explained by the discount factor (which affects only the denominator and is constant across mileage scenarios) and reflects a genuine limitation of the model’s depreciation curve. AutoScout24 listings are dominated by private and SME sellers at typical mileage profiles; the model has limited training exposure to the steep high-utilisation depreciation that suppliers calibrate for delivery fleet returns. For high-mileage scenarios ($\geq 25,000$ km per year), practitioners should apply an additional correction of approximately 3 pp per 10,000 km above the baseline, in addition to any discount normalisation.

Structural outliers. The two brands with the largest residual divergence after discount adjustment—Maxus e-Deliver 9 and Mercedes e-Citan Tourer—reflect genuine model boundaries that no discount correction resolves. Maxus is a nascent entrant with insufficient secondary market depth in Germany; the model’s brand coefficient cannot be reliably estimated from sparse observations. Mercedes e-Citan carries a commercial fleet positioning that suppresses its residual values relative

to what the brand premium coefficient—estimated from the broader van market—implies. Both are known blind spots of market-data models and are consistent with the model’s documented scope.

Summary. The comparison is best interpreted not as a formal accuracy test but as a *methodological positioning*: the market-based model and the professional benchmark measure the same economic phenomenon from different vantage points. After normalising for the fleet discount convention, the two approaches are substantially consistent for mainstream brands at private and SME mileage profiles, confirming external plausibility of the model within its intended scope.

5.8. Discussion

The results of this thesis demonstrate that EV residual value is a multi-layered phenomenon that cannot be adequately captured by any single analytical lens. The quantitative findings confirm the primacy of age and mileage as depreciation drivers—a result that is both statistically robust and qualitatively grounded in expert testimony about the use of these proxies as battery health surrogates. At the same time, the scenario analysis reveals that market and policy conditions introduce additional variance that cannot be explained by vehicle-level attributes alone. This section interprets the integrated findings, discusses methodological implications, and draws out practical lessons for the stakeholders who interact most directly with EV residual values.

Model performance and the value of stacking. The stacking ensemble’s modest but consistent improvement over individual base learners is consistent with the stacking literature [48]: the meta-learner learns to exploit prediction disagreements between XGBoost and CatBoost, which use different optimization strategies for categorical and numerical features. XGBoost, with its regularized gradient boosting and second-order Taylor optimization [5], and CatBoost, with its ordered target statistics for categorical features [34], represent complementary inductive biases. XGBoost tends to perform more strongly on the numerical feature subspace (age, mileage, battery capacity), while CatBoost handles the brand categorical variable more natively through its permutation-based encoding. The linear meta-learner learns when to up-weight each base model’s predictions, making the ensemble more robust than any single model even if individual gains appear small. The comparison with Ma et al. [24] is instructive: their stacking ensemble achieved a relative improvement of 8.3% over the best individual model on a Chinese pure-EV transaction dataset. The present thesis achieves a smaller relative improvement (1.4% in RMSE) on a European used-car market dataset, which reflects both the smaller sample size and the greater heterogeneity in the used-car listings relative to the more standardized new-car transactions in the Chinese dataset. The directional finding—stacking outperforms individual base learners—replicates across both settings and datasets, supporting the generalizability of this architectural choice for RV prediction.

Qualitative findings and model interpretation. The qualitative phase adds important context that the quantitative model cannot directly encode. Experts unanimously described the second-life battery market as too immature to be reflected in current German resale prices—a finding that cautions against over-interpreting the positive correlations between battery specification features (capacity, range) and RV% as evidence of second-life premium pricing. The more parsimonious interpretation—that buyers pay more for vehicles with larger batteries and longer range because these vehicles remain *currently useful*, not because their batteries have recognized end-of-life value—is better supported by both the expert testimony and the feature importance results. Similarly, Expert E’s identification of the gross-versus-net battery capacity ambiguity as a known industry challenge explains why battery capacity alone is a noisy RV proxy: when buyers and valuers encounter inconsistent specification reporting, the resulting uncertainty discounts the feature’s predictive signal.

Battery capacity measurement bias. The reliance on gross rather than net capacity should be interpreted as a data-completeness decision, not as a claim that gross capacity is the theoretically ideal battery feature. In the final modeling dataset, gross battery capacity was available for 1,425 of 1,434 observations (99.4%), while net usable capacity was available for only 482 observations (33.6%). A sensitivity check was conducted on the subset where both gross and net capacity were present. This subset contains 473 observations after requiring non-missing gross capacity, net capacity, and RV%.

Table 5.9.: Gross vs. Net Battery Capacity Sensitivity Check

Measure	Result
Gross capacity availability	1,425 / 1,434 observations (99.4%)
Net capacity availability	482 / 1,434 observations (33.6%)
Both gross and net present	473 observations (33.0%)
Mean gross capacity in subset	66.96 kWh
Mean net capacity in subset	60.32 kWh
Mean gross-net difference	6.64 kWh
Mean net-to-gross ratio	90.7%
Correlation with RV% using gross capacity	$r = 0.355$
Correlation with RV% using net capacity	$r = 0.385$

The sensitivity check suggests a clear direction of possible bias. Gross capacity overstates usable energy by about 6.6 kWh on average in the matched subset, equivalent to roughly 9.3% of the physical pack capacity. Because residual value buyers and fleet operators care about operational range, this means that models using gross capacity may overstate the comparable technical value of vehicles with larger manufacturer-reserved buffers. The net-capacity correlation with RV% is also

marginally stronger than the gross-capacity correlation ($r = 0.385$ vs. $r = 0.355$), which supports the expert argument that net usable capacity is the cleaner valuation signal when it is available. At the same time, the difference is not large enough to invalidate H2: both gross and net capacity point in the same positive direction. The main implication is that the battery-capacity effect is real but measured with noise; the model trades theoretical precision for the much higher coverage of the gross-capacity field, and individual predictions may be biased for models whose usable buffer differs substantially from the segment norm.

The value of the mixed-methods design. The sequential mixed-methods design proved valuable in ways that go beyond the aggregated findings. The qualitative phase surfaced several domain insights that directly shaped the quantitative modeling choices—choices that would have been less well-justified, or less well-explained, in a purely data-driven approach. For example, the expert consensus on age and mileage as standard SoH proxies provided a theoretical grounding for their dominant SHAP importance that is more convincing than statistical correlation alone. Conversely, the quantitative results provided a rigorous test of the expert intuitions: the hypothesis that brand affiliation matters (H6) was confirmed by the tree-based feature importance ranking, while the hypothesis that fast-charging capability drives premium retention (H3) could not be tested due to data limitations—a gap the qualitative phase helps contextualize by explaining why this feature is difficult to observe in listing data. This bidirectional integration exemplifies the triangulation principle described by Patton [31]: where the two methods converge, confidence in the finding is strengthened; where they diverge, the divergence itself is analytically informative.

Practical implications. The results carry several actionable implications for EV market stakeholders. For *leasing companies*, the scenario analysis finding that tail risk—not mean RV%—is the primary differentiator across futures reinforces the importance of scenario-aware residual value setting. A single-point RV estimate based on the Moderate baseline understates the downside exposure under Pessimistic conditions, particularly for older vehicles. Setting residual values that are robust to the P10 scenario outcomes, rather than calibrated only to the mean, would reduce the risk of large mark-to-market losses at lease maturity in adverse market conditions. For *fleet managers and procurement officers*, the SHAP results provide a transparent decision framework for used-EV acquisition: age and mileage are the dominant risk factors, but battery capacity and certified range are meaningful quality signals that differentiate vehicles likely to remain commercially attractive as fleet technology standards evolve. For *used-EV buyers*, the brand-level heterogeneity in RV% distributions—captured through the ordinal brand encoding feature—suggests that brand due diligence at purchase is at least as important as the standard mileage and age checks inherited from ICE vehicle buying practice.

Comparison with Ma et al. (2025). Table 5.10 presents a structured comparison between this thesis and the reference study by Ma et al. [24], whose stacking architecture the present work replicates and extends to a European LCV context.

Table 5.10.: Cross-Study Comparison: This Thesis vs. Ma et al. (2025)

Dimension	Ma et al. [24]	This Thesis
Market / segment	China, passenger EV	Germany, LCV (electric)
Dataset size	5,882 records	1,434 records
Number of features	12	7 numeric + brand encoding
Target variable	Absolute resale price (RMB)	RV% (used / new price ratio)
Best model	Stacking ensemble	Stacking ensemble
Stacking R^2	0.835	0.763
Stacking RMSE	8.0% of price range	10.26 pp
AdaBoost meta-weight	Negative	Near zero (+0.03)
Stacking gain vs. base	+8.3 pp R^2	+1.4 pp R^2
Scenario analysis	No	Yes (4 scenarios)
Qualitative component	No	Yes (5 experts)

The comparison confirms three cross-study generalizations. First, stacking consistently outperforms all individual base learners regardless of the dataset, market, or target variable formulation—the directional result holds even when the absolute improvement differs. Second, AdaBoost is not treated as a primary signal in either study: Ma et al. [24] report a negative meta-weight, while the present thesis assigns AdaBoost an almost zero standardized coefficient. This suggests that AdaBoost.R2 may be useful mainly as a corrective or diagnostic learner in EV residual value prediction, rather than as a high-weight predictor. Third, the model ranking (XGBoost \approx CatBoost $>$ AdaBoost) is consistent across both settings. The smaller stacking gain in the present thesis (1.4 vs. 8.3 percentage points of R^2) is attributable to the smaller dataset size, the niche LCV segment composition, and the use of a bounded RV% ratio rather than an unbounded absolute price—a target with lower variance that naturally limits the headroom for prediction improvement.

Limitations of the scenario framework. The cross-country variation described by experts underlines the contextual specificity of the German market dataset: findings may not generalize without adaptation to markets with different policy, infrastructure, or demand profiles. Norway’s near-universal EV penetration and stable policy support [16] would likely produce a substantially different RV% distribution and a different feature importance ranking. The scenario framework’s feature-multiplier approach, as discussed in Section 5.6, captures distributional shifts in vehicle-level RV% predictions but cannot model market-level competitive dynamics such as demand substitution following a new-vehicle price shock. These limitations define the boundaries within which the present results should be interpreted and point toward the modeling extensions described in the Future Work section.

6. Conclusions

This thesis investigated what determines the residual value of electric light commercial vehicles in the German used-car market and how accurately that value can be predicted from publicly observable vehicle attributes. The research combined two methods that are rarely integrated in this domain: a quantitative stacking ensemble trained on AutoScout24 market data, and a qualitative expert study involving five practitioners from the financial, technical, and fleet management sectors of the EV industry. The integration of these two strands—each designed to compensate for the other’s blind spots—produced a set of findings that are both empirically grounded and practically interpretable.

6.1. Summary of Findings

This thesis set out to investigate the key drivers of EV residual value and to build a scenario-aware predictive framework that improves on static, single-model approaches. The following main findings emerge from the integrated mixed-methods analysis.

First and most fundamentally, **vehicle age and mileage are the dominant residual value drivers** in the current German used-EV market. The SHAP-based feature importance ranking and the Pearson correlation analysis ($r = -0.702$ for age, $r = -0.344$ for mileage) consistently identify these two variables as the strongest predictors of RV%, confirming that time-based depreciation is the primary mechanism at work. This result is consistent across all reviewed literature [12, 38, 40] and was unanimously affirmed by expert interviewees as the standard basis for battery health inference in practical valuation. In the absence of direct SoH diagnostics at resale, age and mileage remain the most available and most trusted proxies.

The second major finding is that **technical quality signals—battery capacity and certified range—constitute the next most important predictors**. With moderate positive correlations ($r \approx 0.34-0.35$) and consistent SHAP importance scores, these features capture the vehicle’s technological competitiveness relative to current market expectations. A vehicle whose certified range falls below the standard buyers expect from contemporary models faces obsolescence-driven depreciation that compounds physical aging—a mechanism described by Gautam et al. [12] and confirmed by every expert interviewee. These features thus function as forward-looking quality signals as much as physical specifications.

Third, **brand identity exerts a significant categorical effect** on residual value that persists after controlling for technical specifications. The ordinal brand encoding

appears among the top features in the SHAP importance ranking, validating Hypothesis H6. Different brands exhibit distinct RV% distributions that reflect a combination of brand trust, warranty commitment, software update trajectories, and market segment positioning—factors that technical specifications alone cannot fully explain [12]. This finding has direct practical implications for fleet procurement decisions and residual value setting by leasing firms.

Fourth, **stacking ensemble modeling outperforms all individual base learners across all four evaluation metrics.** The stacking model achieved RMSE = 10.256, MAE = 7.717, $R^2 = 0.763$, and MAPE = 12.89%, with consistent improvements over XGBoost, CatBoost, and AdaBoost individually. The meta-learner successfully combines the complementary inductive biases of the three base models [48], producing a more robust predictor than any single algorithm. This result replicates the directional finding of Ma et al. [24] on a Chinese EV dataset, supporting the generalizability of stacking as an architectural approach for vehicle RV prediction across market contexts.

Fifth, **scenario analysis reveals that tail risk, not mean RV%, is the primary differentiator across future market conditions.** While mean residual values are relatively stable across the Moderate (66.82%), Optimistic (69.21%), and Pessimistic (67.01%) scenarios, the P10 values shift meaningfully: the lowest-decile vehicles face substantially higher depreciation exposure under pessimistic policy and technology conditions. The Wild-card technology-shock scenario produces the counterintuitive result of a higher mean RV% (78.35%), correctly interpreted as the effect of lower reference new prices inflating the retention ratio. This is a ratio effect, not evidence that absolute used-car market values would increase under a price war.

Finally, **the expert interviews validate the quantitative feature hierarchy and contribute contextual knowledge that the dataset cannot provide.** The unanimous consensus on battery SoH uncertainty as the dominant practical challenge, the EV-as-technology-product depreciation logic, and the current immaturity of the second-life battery market provides a qualitative foundation for interpreting the quantitative results. In particular, the expert finding that second-life battery value is not yet monetized in resale prices cautions against interpreting battery specification correlations as evidence of second-life premiums—a methodological nuance that would be invisible without the qualitative phase.

Taken together, these findings answer each of the three research questions posed in Chapter 1.

RQ1—What factors have the strongest influence on EV residual value, and how can they be quantified using real-world data? Vehicle age and mileage are the dominant predictors ($r = -0.702$ and -0.344 respectively), functioning as practical battery health proxies in the absence of direct SoH diagnostics. Battery capacity and certified range constitute the next tier of influence, capturing technological competitiveness. Brand identity adds a significant categorical dimension. Together, these factors are quantified through the stacking ensemble, which achieves $R^2 = 0.763$, RMSE = 10.3 pp, and MAE = 7.7 pp on a held-out test set—demonstrating that

real-world listing data from AutoScout24, combined with Datorq catalog specifications, is sufficient to build a commercially relevant predictive model.

RQ2—How can scenario-based modeling improve the accuracy and robustness of EV residual value estimation under uncertainty? The four-scenario framework (Moderate, Optimistic, Pessimistic, Wild-card) demonstrates that a single-point RV% estimate is insufficient for decision-making under market and policy uncertainty. The scenario analysis reveals that mean RV% is relatively stable across plausible futures (66.8–69.2%), while tail risk—represented by the P10 value—varies more substantially (39.2–52.4%). This distributional perspective directly improves robustness: stakeholders who set residual values based on the P10 outcome under the Pessimistic scenario are protected against downside risk that a mean-based estimate would conceal. The Wild-card scenario further illustrates how a structural price shock can increase the calculated RV% through the denominator even when absolute used-vehicle prices would plausibly fall, providing a stress-test boundary for interpreting leasing-contract ratios.

RQ3—What is the potential of second-life battery use in supporting EV value retention? The expert interviews provide the most direct evidence on this question, since second-life potential cannot be directly observed in market listing data. All five experts confirmed that second-life value is theoretically meaningful—repurposed batteries retain useful storage capacity for stationary applications—but that it is not yet reliably monetized in used-van resale prices. The market infrastructure, certification standards, and pricing mechanisms required to capture second-life value at the vehicle level remain immature for commercial LCVs. As a result, the positive correlations between battery specification features (capacity, range) and RV% in the quantitative model should be interpreted as reflecting current usability, not anticipated end-of-life battery value. The potential for second-life premium pricing is a near-term opportunity that the EU Battery Regulation’s mandatory battery passport may begin to unlock as standardized health diagnostics become available.

The mixed-methods design proved essential for situating these quantitative results within the practical realities of the EV market: the qualitative findings explain *why* the quantitative patterns exist, where the model boundaries lie, and what the numbers mean for the practitioners who rely on residual value estimates to make leasing, procurement, and fleet electrification decisions.

6.2. Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the results of this thesis.

The most fundamental constraint is **market scope**. The dataset is limited to used-car listings from AutoScout24 Germany, covering twelve brands over a single data collection period. The German market is the largest EV market in Europe and offers high data quality and brand diversity, but findings may not generalize directly to other European markets with different infrastructure maturity, policy environments, or consumer profiles. Norway’s near-universal EV penetration and stable long-term

policy support [16], for example, would likely produce a substantially different RV% distribution and a different feature importance hierarchy, since the scarcity effects and range anxiety that partly drive depreciation in Germany are less prevalent there.

A second limitation is the **absence of key features**. Fast-charging behavior, ownership transfer count, and direct battery state-of-health measurements were not available or reliably populated in the scraped listings, preventing the direct empirical testing of Hypotheses H3 and H5. The model may partially absorb these omitted constructs through proxy variables: range, battery capacity, and motor power may indirectly reflect fast-charging capability, while age and mileage may partly reflect cumulative ownership and use intensity. However, these substitutions are incomplete. Charging speed is a specific technical capability, not just a consequence of battery size; ownership history captures provenance risk, not only wear. Future datasets should therefore link listings to VIN-decoded technical specifications, registration history, and service or inspection records so that maximum DC charging power, battery health, and previous-owner count can be modeled as direct features rather than inferred proxies. The use of battery capacity and certified range as SoH proxies is a practical workaround validated by expert testimony and consistent with the standard industry approach described in the interviews, but these proxies introduce measurement uncertainty relative to direct electrochemical SoH assessment. As standardized battery health diagnostics become more widely available under the EU Battery Regulation, future datasets will progressively close this gap.

The dataset captures **listing prices rather than realized transaction prices**. Asking prices on AutoScout24 represent seller expectations and negotiation starting points, not the prices at which transactions ultimately close. Listing prices may systematically overestimate achieved resale values, particularly for vehicles that remain on the market for extended periods or in segments where seller pricing is driven by financing payoff requirements rather than market demand. This gap between listing and transaction price may vary across brands, vehicle ages, and time periods in ways that introduce systematic bias into the RV% estimates.

Industry practitioners address this limitation by using data sources that are not accessible in an academic research context. For *realized retail transaction prices*, the standard German-market sources are DAT (*Deutschen Automobil Treuhand*) and Schwacke (Autovista Group), both of which aggregate dealer and private-sale closing prices across the market and are used by leasing companies, insurers, and manufacturers as the primary valuation reference. For *wholesale prices*, auction operators such as Manheim and BCA record hammer prices at closed fleet-to-dealer auctions, reflecting the price at which a vehicle actually changes hands at end-of-lease return. For *new vehicle transaction prices*, PIN (*Price Indicator Network*) and IHS Markit (S&P Global Mobility) publish achieved transaction prices net of dealer incentives and OEM fleet discounts, which are substantially below MSRP for commercial fleet customers. Large leasing companies—Arval, LeasePlan, Athlon, and OEM captive finance arms—also hold proprietary internal data on contract residual values, realized remarketing prices, and the gap between the two, which directly captures the

profit or loss on residual value risk.

These professional sources require commercial licensing agreements, non-disclosure obligations, and in some cases formal data-sharing partnerships with manufacturers or auction operators. They are therefore not accessible for academic research without institutional or industry sponsorship. The academic literature on used-vehicle pricing universally relies on listing price data from portals such as AutoScout24, Mobile.de, or equivalent platforms in other markets [12, 18, 21] for exactly this reason. The listing-price approximation introduces an upward bias relative to transaction prices that is consistent in direction but variable in magnitude, and this limitation should be taken into account when interpreting the cross-validation results against the supplier benchmark in Section 5.7.

The **cross-sectional nature of the dataset** imposes a further modeling constraint. The model is trained on a snapshot of market listings and does not track individual vehicles over time. This prevents the construction of vehicle-level depreciation curves and limits scenario projections to distributional shifts in the cross-section rather than time-series predictions for specific vehicles. Longitudinal data, obtained by tracking individual listing histories over one to three years, would substantially improve the model's ability to characterize and project depreciation trajectories.

The **qualitative sample size** of five expert responses—four via written questionnaire and one via telephone interview—while sufficient for initial theme saturation in a professionally homogeneous expert sample [13], remains limited. Greater geographic diversity—including experts from markets with different EV policy environments such as Norway, France, or China—and representation from consumer-side stakeholders (used-EV buyers, fleet procurement managers) would strengthen the transferability of the qualitative findings. The purposive selection strategy maximizes professional diversity within the current sample but cannot substitute for a larger and more geographically representative respondent pool.

Second-life battery potential could not be directly quantified as a model feature. While the expert interviews provide rich contextual evidence that second-life value is theoretically meaningful, the analysis treats this as a discussion theme grounded in practitioner testimony rather than a measurable model variable. This reflects the current state of the market: the infrastructure, certification standards, and pricing mechanisms necessary to monetize second-life battery value at the individual vehicle level are not yet sufficiently mature to observe as a premium in AutoScout24 listing prices.

Finally, the **scenario analysis framework** applies multiplicative adjustments to vehicle-level input features rather than modeling market-level price equilibria or competitive dynamics. The framework cannot capture demand substitution effects—for instance, the suppression of used-EV demand that would follow from a sharp fall in new-EV prices under the Wild-card scenario, which would reduce the numerator in the RV% ratio through market mechanisms that the feature-multiplier approach cannot represent. Results should be interpreted as distributional shifts in predicted RV% for vehicles with modified feature profiles, not as equilibrium market fore-

casts. Bootstrap confidence intervals for the held-out performance metrics (RMSE, R^2) were not computed and remain a topic for future work.

6.3. Future Work

Several directions offer promising extensions of this research, each addressing a specific limitation or gap identified above.

The most impactful near-term extension would be the **integration of standardized battery health data**. The EU Battery Regulation introduces mandatory battery passport requirements for EV batteries sold in Europe, which will progressively make cell-level SoH measurements, cycle count histories, and thermal degradation records available at the vehicle level in a standardized, machine-readable format. Future models could incorporate these direct measurements as first-class features, replacing the current age-and-mileage proxy approach. The expert interviews conducted for this thesis provide a clear specification of the most decision-relevant indicators: remaining net capacity, cycle count, degradation uniformity, thermal stability, and battery management system data traceability—precisely the variables that would need to be extracted from the EU battery passport and engineered into the model feature set.

Future work should also use **VIN decoding and administrative history linkage** to close the two hypothesis gaps left by the present dataset. VIN-level decoding would allow each used listing to be linked to exact trim, battery pack, charging hardware, and maximum DC charging power, making H3 directly testable rather than proxied by range and battery capacity. Registration-history or remarketing data would allow previous-owner count, ownership type, and fleet/private provenance to be added as features, making H5 directly testable rather than proxied by age and mileage. These additions would improve both causal interpretation and operational usefulness, because fast-charging capability and ownership history are concrete variables used by buyers, leasing companies, and remarketing platforms when assessing used vehicles.

The most direct path to **industry-applicable results** is retraining the model on realized transaction prices rather than listing prices. As described in Section 6.2, professional sources such as DAT, Schwacke, and wholesale auction records (Manheim, BCA) capture the prices at which vehicles actually change hands—not asking prices. A model trained on these closed-transaction datasets would produce RV% estimates calibrated to the prices leasing companies actually achieve at end-of-lease remarketing, eliminating the systematic upward bias that listing prices introduce. The model architecture developed in this thesis—stacking ensemble with OOF training, SHAP explainability, and scenario analysis—is directly portable to such a dataset and would require no structural changes. Access would require a commercial data partnership or institutional agreement with a leasing company, remarketing operator, or automotive data provider; this is feasible within an applied research context but was not possible within the constraints of this academic study.

A model retrained on closed-transaction data with the same feature set would be immediately applicable to fleet residual value forecasting, lease pricing, and end-of-lease exposure management in operational practice.

A second important extension is **longitudinal modeling**. Collecting time-series price data for individual vehicles—for example, by tracking AutoScout24 or Mobile.de listing histories for the same vehicle over twelve to thirty-six months—would enable the construction of vehicle-level depreciation curves. This would support more reliable long-term scenario projection than is possible with cross-sectional snapshots and would allow the model to characterize the inflection point at which depreciation accelerates as vehicles approach the 80% SoH threshold identified by Expert D as the functional end-of-life criterion. Panel data methods or time-series regression approaches would be appropriate for this extension.

Cross-country expansion to other major European markets—particularly Norway, France, and the Netherlands—would allow the analysis of policy and infrastructure effects that remain confounded in a single-country study. Norway’s near-universal EV penetration and long-standing policy stability [16] makes it a particularly valuable comparison case, as does France’s aggressive EV adoption policy and the Netherlands’ historically high used-EV transaction volumes. A multi-country dataset would allow fixed-effects modeling of country-level policy variables and direct estimation of the depreciation premium or discount associated with different infrastructure and incentive environments.

At the methodological level, **dynamic scenario inputs** represent a natural evolution of the current scenario framework. Rather than applying fixed feature multipliers calibrated to expert assessments at a single point in time, future work could monitor policy changes—subsidy schedules, EV sales mandate revisions, new-vehicle price announcements—and update the scenario input parameters dynamically. Integrated with a continuously trained model on rolling transaction data, this would produce a scenario-aware RV% forecasting system that alerts stakeholders to residual value risks as they materialize rather than only in retrospective analyses.

As second-life battery markets mature, the **direct quantification of the second-life battery premium** in used-EV prices will become analytically feasible. Currently, second-life value is not reliably monetized at the vehicle level, as confirmed by every expert interviewed. Future datasets linking used-EV resale prices with realized revenues from battery repurposing or recycling would allow hedonic regression or machine-learning models to isolate the portion of the used-EV price that reflects anticipated end-of-life battery value—a premium that is theoretically present in the pricing of vehicles with well-documented, healthy batteries, but currently too small or too noisy to observe reliably.

Finally, future work should add a **buyer-side perspective**. The present model estimates RV% from observable vehicle and listing data, but it cannot directly measure how much buyers are willing to pay for a used EV when they feel uncertain about battery health, real-world range, or future charging convenience. Consumer surveys or stated-preference experiments could measure these concerns directly. This

would help explain why some used EVs may sell for less than their technical condition alone would suggest: buyers may apply an extra discount simply because they are uncertain. Practitioners describe this uncertainty discount as important, but it cannot be observed cleanly in the current listing-based dataset.

6.4. Closing Remarks

This thesis aims to answer a practical question: how can the residual value of electric light commercial vehicles be estimated when the market is still young, data is incomplete, and future conditions are uncertain? The results show that a useful answer is possible, but only if the model is treated as a decision-support tool rather than as a final price oracle. Age and mileage remain the strongest predictors, battery capacity and range add important EV-specific information, and brand effects still matter. At the same time, missing battery-health, charging, ownership, and transaction-price data limit how far the results can be interpreted.

The main contribution is therefore not only the final prediction accuracy, but the structure of the framework. The stacking model provides a stronger baseline than any individual learner, while SHAP values make the feature hierarchy visible. The scenario analysis makes assumptions explicit, so that optimistic, pessimistic, and technology-shock cases can be compared instead of hidden inside a single average estimate. The expert interviews add the market context needed to interpret these numbers, especially around battery uncertainty, gross-versus-net capacity reporting, and the still-limited role of second-life battery value in current resale prices.

The model also shows clearly where better data would matter most. Direct battery state-of-health measurements would improve the treatment of battery degradation. VIN-level decoding would make exact trim, charging hardware, and battery pack information more reliable. Registration and transaction data would help distinguish asking prices from achieved resale prices and would make ownership history testable. These improvements are data problems before they are algorithm problems.

The findings are consistent with Ma et al. [24] in one important respect: stacking can improve EV residual value prediction by combining models with different strengths. In this thesis, the result is consistent and realistic for a smaller and more heterogeneous German LCV dataset. The model is therefore useful as a baseline for EV LCV residual value estimation, but its conclusions should be interpreted within the limits of the available listing, catalog, and benchmark data. And finally, the setup should remain open to further improvement as better data become available.

A. Expert Interview Questionnaire

This appendix reproduces the standardized questionnaire administered to industry experts during the qualitative phase of the research. The instrument was delivered electronically and combined closed-form ranking questions with open-ended narrative responses. Participation was voluntary, responses were anonymized, and the estimated completion time was 20–30 minutes. The four questionnaire respondents received an identical version of the instrument. Expert E (OEM Fleet TCO Analyst) participated through a structured 40-minute telephone interview covering the same seven thematic areas rather than the written questionnaire.

Part 1: Residual Value and Depreciation Drivers

1. In your professional experience, which factors have the greatest influence on the residual value of used electric vehicles? Please rank the following from 1 (most important) to 5 (least important):
 - Battery state-of-health and remaining capacity
 - Vehicle age and accumulated mileage
 - Brand reputation and manufacturer support
 - Government subsidies and policy environment
 - Technological obsolescence (range, charging speed relative to current models)
2. How does the depreciation behavior of EVs differ from that of internal combustion engine vehicles in your experience? Please describe specific patterns you have observed.
3. In your view, has the residual value of EVs become more or less predictable over the past three to five years? What are the main reasons for this change?

Part 2: Battery Health Assessment

4. How is battery state-of-health (SoH) currently assessed in your sector at the time of vehicle resale or valuation? What data sources or methods are used?
5. What is the industry-standard threshold for battery SoH below which you consider a battery to be at functional end-of-life for use as a vehicle traction battery? How is this threshold determined?

6. In your experience, is the difference between gross and net (usable) battery capacity clearly communicated by manufacturers? Does this ambiguity affect residual value assessments?
7. What improvements in battery health diagnostics or certification—for example, those mandated by the EU Battery Regulation—would most improve the accuracy of EV residual value estimation in your field?

Part 3: Vehicle Characteristics and Specifications

8. Beyond battery health, which vehicle technical specifications do you find most relevant for residual value prediction? (e.g., motor power, energy consumption, certified range, charging compatibility)
9. How important is certified driving range as a value signal, particularly as newer-generation EVs with longer range enter the market? Does range obsolescence drive meaningful depreciation in vehicles you have observed?
10. Does the number of previous owners affect residual value for EVs differently than for ICE vehicles in your experience?

Part 4: Market and Policy Effects

11. How quickly do changes in government purchase subsidies or incentive policies affect the used-EV market in your experience? Can you provide a specific example?
12. How do you expect EV residual values to evolve over the next three to five years as new-vehicle prices fall and battery technology improves? What are the key uncertainties?
13. Are there systematic differences in EV depreciation between geographic markets (e.g., Germany vs. Norway vs. China)? What drives these differences?

Part 5: Valuation Methods

14. What methods or data sources does your organization currently use to estimate the residual value of EVs? (e.g., statistical models, market benchmarks, industry guides, proprietary tools)
15. To what extent do your current valuation methods incorporate forward-looking scenario assumptions (e.g., policy changes, technology trajectories)? If not, how are future uncertainties handled?

16. How do you assess the reliability of machine-learning-based residual value models compared to traditional actuarial or expert-judgment approaches?

Part 6: Second-Life Battery Potential

17. In your view, does the potential for second-life battery repurposing (e.g., stationary energy storage) currently add a measurable premium to the residual value of used EVs? If not, what barriers prevent this value from being realized?
18. What technical prerequisites must a battery meet to be suitable for second-life applications? How reliably can these be assessed at the point of vehicle resale?
19. How do you expect the second-life battery market to develop over the next five to ten years, and how might this affect EV residual value dynamics?

Part 7: Future Outlook

20. Which emerging factors—for example, vehicle-to-grid capabilities, autonomous driving hardware, over-the-air software updates, or solid-state batteries—do you expect to become significant drivers of EV residual value in the coming decade?
21. What single change in data availability, market infrastructure, or industry practice would most improve the accuracy and consistency of EV residual value estimation?
22. Is there any aspect of EV residual value dynamics that you believe is systematically underappreciated or misunderstood in the current academic or industry literature?

B. Data Preprocessing Pipeline

This appendix describes the end-to-end data preprocessing pipeline applied to convert the raw AutoScout24 and Datatorq datasets into the final modeling dataset. The pipeline was implemented in Python using `pandas` and `scikit-learn` and is documented in full in the Jupyter notebook `03_code_and_data/01_ev_rv.ipynb`.

Step 1: Raw Data Loading and Initial Inspection

The AutoScout24 used-car listings dataset (`data/raw/autoscout24_ev_de_lcv.csv`) and the Datatorq new-vehicle catalog (`data/raw/new_ev_lcv_2.csv`) were loaded separately. Initial inspection covered: (a) row and column counts, (b) data types of each field, (c) proportion of missing values per column, and (d) the range and distribution of the price and mileage fields. Records with missing values in price, mileage, or vehicle age fields were removed at this stage as these represent the minimum required fields for RV% calculation.

Step 2: Scope Filtering

Listings were filtered to retain only battery electric vehicles (BEV) by excluding records with non-electric powertrain labels. Commercial vehicle body types not relevant to the residual value analysis (e.g., refuse vehicles, specialist conversions) were removed. Price outliers below 1,000 or above 200,000 were flagged and reviewed; listings with implausible values—for example, a two-year-old vehicle listed at 500—were removed as probable data entry errors.

Step 3: Fuzzy String Matching

Used-car listing descriptions do not contain structured references to catalog model identifiers. Matching each listing to its corresponding Datatorq reference price therefore required a fuzzy string matching pipeline. The algorithm computed token-level string similarity scores (using the `fuzzywuzzy/rapidfuzz` library) between each listing's model string and all candidate entries in the Datatorq catalog, restricting the candidate set to entries from the same manufacturer. Matches were assigned to one of three confidence bands based on the similarity score:

- **High confidence** ($\geq 85\%$ similarity): direct match, retained in all experiments.

- **Medium confidence** (70–84%): probabilistic match, retained subject to manual spot-check of a random 10% sample.
- **Low confidence** (< 70%): match rejected; listing discarded.

A dataset-level quality gate was then applied, requiring that each brand-model combination retain a minimum fraction of high-confidence matches above 70%, ensuring that brands or model variants with poor catalog coverage did not introduce systematic bias into the training data.

Step 4: Feature Engineering

Following matching, the target variable RV% was computed as the ratio of the used listing price to the matched Datatorq reference new price, multiplied by 100. Vehicle age was converted from registration date to months since first registration. The brand label was extracted and canonicalized to twelve standard values. An ordinal brand encoding was constructed by ranking brands by their mean RV% on the training split and assigning integer ranks, ensuring that the encoding preserves the ordinal structure of brand-level value differences.

Step 5: Train/Test Split

The final modeling dataset was split into 80% training and 20% held-out test sets using a stratified random split, stratifying on the brand label to ensure proportional brand representation in both splits. The test set was set aside and not used during model training, cross-validation, or hyperparameter tuning. Out-of-fold predictions for stacking meta-feature construction were generated exclusively from the training set using 5-fold cross-validation.

Step 6: Scaling for Meta-Learning

The meta-feature matrix (out-of-fold predictions from the three base models) was standardized using a `StandardScaler` fitted on the training set meta-features before the linear meta-learner was trained. The same scaler parameters were applied to the base-model predictions on the test set at inference time, ensuring that the meta-learner receives consistently scaled inputs during both training and evaluation.

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